

Falcon

Foreseeing *the next* generation of Aircraft

D3.2. Report on first experimental test
of high-lift wing with flap-cove seal
in AWB

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List of acronyms	
AoA	Angle of Attack
AWB	Aeroacoustic wind tunnel Braunschweig
BL	Boundary Layer
DLR	German Aerospace Center
DP	Data point
F15LS	<i>Name of a rather large wing model</i>
F16	<i>Name of a small wing model suitable for tests in AWB</i>
FSI	Fluid-structure interaction
FLE	Flap leading edge
FTE	Flap trailing edge
HW	Hot-wire
IPCT	image pattern correlation technique
L80	<i>Seal with an unclamped/free length of 80mm</i>

LBM	Lattice Boltzmann Method
PIV	Particle Image Velocimetry
PSI	Pounds per square inch, <i>an Imperial/US customary unit</i>
TC	Test case
TPU	Thermoplastic polyurethane, <i>a material</i>
WLE	Wing leading edge
WMLES	Wall-Modelled Large Eddy Simulation
w.r.t.	with respect to
WT	Wind tunnel
WTE	Wing trailing edge
WTT	Wind tunnel test
WP	Work Package
X95	<i>a rail system produced by the company Qioptiq Photonics GmbH & Co KG</i>

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1. Introduction

The AWB wind tunnel test campaign (Figure 1) was conducted in June and July 2025. The test features the TC2 wing flap cove seal at the 2-element high-lift wing model F15LSmod.

Figure 1: FALCON main test on flap cove of F15LS mod

The WP3 experiment was initially planned to be conducted with the DLR-F16, a 2D wing model with a clean chord length of $c=300\text{mm}$. In the early stages of the project, the results of DLR's model analysis and test design raised concerns regarding too small model geometry for the objectives of a successful fluid-structure experiment. Hence, DLR proposed to make use of the 4 times larger flap cove of DLR-F15LS, a 2D wing model with a clean chord length of 1200mm and a model scale of $\sim 1:3.7$.

DLR conducted a pre-test with model configurations made of standard parts as well as reduced instrumentation (cameras + far-field microphones) in Nov-Dec 2024.

The test started by reproducing and extending knowledge on a state-of-the-art fluid-structure interaction experiment by testing a Hron-Turek like cylinder with a splitterplate ("Conf-C"). The test with a very soft foam seal confirmed the rich physics of different Reynolds number dependent vortex shedding regimes ($Re_D=3 \cdot 10^4 \dots 9 \cdot 10^5$) in the cylinder wake that was mapped by Williamson 1996 [<https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.fl.28.010196.002401>].

Figure 2: Fluid-structure-interaction pre-Test with foam material in the wake of a cylinder

However, the rich wake flow physics could not be seen when using even moderately stiff sheet material made of polystyrene (PS) and polyvinyl chloride (PVC).

The second test goal was to replicate the flap cove of the main model. The 8° deflected Conf-C with a steel plate was reused as a make-shift flap; the wing was replicated by Conf-D, a combination of a half-cylinder, U-Steel and a stiff plate for the wing trailing edge as well as a soft plate for the seal.

Figure 3: Flap cove physics replicated with a make-shift experiment using standard materials.

The most important finding of this test was the curving of the seal at rather low velocity, as well as an excitation of the bending mode at a dimensional bending stiffness of 2-5%: The fluid inertial force must

be approximately 20 to 50 times higher than the bending stiffness in order to excite the seal in streamwise direction. This property was helpful for the design of the seals at the main test.

DLR designed more than 60 parts to get the modified F15LS model ready for testing. A crucial contribution was the numerically conducted design of the wing nose contours and the boundary layer fence, as well as the estimation of the model's installation position and the operations range in AWB.

DLR conducted preliminary and final design reviews by subgroup as well as a test readiness review on 05.06.2025. The main test was conducted in June 2025, contains 380 data points and is described in this report.

2. Test Objectives

The main objective of the test is to obtain experimental data related to the mechanical vibration of a wing seal located between the main wing and the deployed flap when the flap is very close to retract position. This was identified as a relevant industrial test case in FALCON and identified as Test Case n°2. (TC2). **The ultimate purpose** is to have experimental data to validate on an ulterior phase the theoretical fluid structure interaction (FSI) tools being developed in FALCON.

FSI is being considered in this experiment under a primary hypothesis to be verified by this experiment. This primary hypothesis is as follows: At a certain geometrical combination of wind speed, angle of attack, flap position relative to the wing there should be established an airflow re-circulation inside the cavity that the wing has to accommodate the flap in fully retracted conditions. This re-circulation is well known in the literature as cavity resonance. This cavity resonance produces aerodynamic pulsating tones that might affect the surrounding structures or seals. Rossiter (1966) studied a rectangular cavity in a transonic wind tunnel obtained the law of harmonic modes and aerodynamic excitation as function of the cavity geometry and inflow conditions. The typical airplane has many cavities with seals and in particular the flap to main wing box is one example. Physically is expected to trigger a cavity resonance that will be influenced by the flexibility of the seal as it forms part of the cavity with in-flow coming from the lower part of the wing and outflow zone from the gap between the flap and the main wing-box. As a result, the seal will vibrate under this cavity resonance excitation causing noise and degrading the material life of the part. Therefore, there is an industrial need to be able to predict this physical interaction to avoid noise and have a robust in-service behavior thru the years of service (seal aging degradation aspects). Also, it is relevant for the academia and research institutions as it provides a bridge on a more challenging benchmark compared with existing literature. ([Turek et al 2006.](#))

Objectives:

1. To verify the cavity resonance hypothesis when the flap-wing box-seal are close together.
2. To be able to measure the acoustic signals, the aerodynamic pressure fluctuations and the seal deformation time histories. To be able to measure the fluid field by PIV techniques.
3. To serve as a basis for FSI benchmark more representative for an industrial concept.

3. Numerical test design

Numerical design study was primarily focused on providing the inputs to the development of the wind tunnel model. Since no larger fluid-structure “two-way” interaction simulation are conducted at this stage of the project, the simulations realize “one-way” predictions solely based on non-flexible rigid geometry description. A numerical design study was conducted using the wall-modelled LES Lattice Boltzmann Method (LBM) simulations using ProLB v2.6.3_dc.

3.1. DLR-F16

DLR-F16 was the originally proposed high-lift wing profile to develop the test setup. The F16 wing has been measured extensively in different wind tunnels and has been used in multiple DLR projects. Results of the F16 measurements are published in the BANC-V (Benchmark for Airframe Noise Computations) workshop. The F16 configuration has both slat and flap deployed. It is an unswept wing configuration which has a clean chord length, c , of 0.3m. Figure 4, shows the three element F16 high-lift wing section. This section was taken at the mean aerodynamic chord of the AIRBUS FNG wing. The one that is used was a 1:13.1 model scale wing section.

Figure 4: DLR-F16 wing profile

Figure 5: F16 flap cove with installed flush mounted seal

It was postulated initially to use the F16 wing with a rigid seal and perform an iterative study. Iterative in terms of combining different seal sizes/shapes and flap settings. Goal was to study the resulting flow field from the rigid seal simulations and identifying what combination of seal size/shape plus the flap setting would provide optimal/critical excitations for a Fluid-Structure-Interaction (FSI) response. Figure 5, shows the F16 flap cove with the seal (provided by AIRBUS) installed (by DLR). To numerically facilitate the correct onset of turbulence on the wing it was jointly agreed between the partners to use the configuration with slat deployed and a take-off setting for the slat and the flap deflection. This case was investigated with $Ma=0.18$ based on the free-stream velocity of 61.53 m/s. Reynolds number resulting from a clean chord length of 0.3m was 1.23 million.

3.1.1. Solver & Numerical settings

Investigation of the F16 wing with a seal was carried out with ProLB v 2.6.3_dc. It employs a hybrid recursive regularization (HRR) scheme to facilitate unsteady simulations, specifically well suited for aeroacoustics, at high Reynolds- and Mach- number.

Figure 6, shows the computational domain used in the simulation. It is a square domain of size $30 \cdot c \times 30 \cdot c$. Three velocity inlet boundary conditions (in green) and a pressure outlet boundary condition (in blue) were used. Wall model boundary condition was applied on the wing surfaces. The domain stretches

~20%c along the spanwise direction as shown in Figure 7. Periodicity was enforced along the spanwise direction. To realize the wing angle of attack, the oncoming flow velocity vectors were rotated accordingly. Mesh independence study was performed on the F16 with seal setup, but the results will only show the final chosen numerical settings.

Initial examination for the fluid-structure interaction effects started with the F16 configuration shown in Figure 8, but a presence of a divergent gap between the slat trailing edge and the wing main element resulted in a flow separation on the suction side of the main element. This led to a choice of configuration which would be the case in the real take-off scenario, see Table 1.

Figure 6: Computational domain with exemplary F16

Figure 7: Spanwise extruded F16, 20%c

Figure 8: Initial F16 configuration with a rigid seal, Slat $\delta_S=25^\circ$, Flap $\delta_F=14^\circ$.

Table 2: Mesh setting parameters

Parameter	Value
Δx_f [m]	6.25×10^{-5}
Δt [s]	1.05×10^{-7}
Spanwise extent Δ_z [m]	0.064
Refinement Levels (N)	10
Time [s]	0.29
No. of nodes (in million)	125

Table 1: Take-off 2 settings for F16 wing

	Value
Slat	18°
Flap	12°

Table 3: Different configurations of the F16 wing with rigid seal

	Slat	Flap
Configuration A	deployed	deployed
Configuration B-I	retracted	deployed
Configuration B-II	retracted	removed

With the F16 configuration mentioned in the Table 1 along the numerical settings defined in the Table 2, several variations of F16 with a rigid seal were performed. The computational meshes are based on hierarchical cartesian grids. These variations were based on the choice of scenarios which would help us understand possible fluid-structure interaction mechanism in the flap cove.

Table 3 shows the configurations simulated to investigate the range in which the vibration frequency should be obtained. According to the AIRBUS, at a full-scale aircraft, during take-off condition, the vibration frequency of the seal was observed at ~ 0 (100 Hz). Since we are operating in the model scale dimensions i.e. 1:13.1, the vibration frequency would accordingly scale to ~ 0 (1000 Hz).

Figure 9: F16 configuration A with a rigid seal, Slat $\delta_S - 18^\circ$, Flap $\delta_F - 12^\circ$.

Figure 10: F16 configuration B-I with a rigid seal, Slat – retracted, Flap $\delta_F - 14^\circ$.

Figure 11: F16 configuration B-II with a rigid seal, Slat – retracted, Flap - removed.

3.1.2. Results

Configuration A

Configuration A, see Figure 9, was the take-off 2 setting with the slat and flap deployed. The flow conditions were as specified before in the section. Mesh refinement study was carried out using this configuration. Based on the smallest dimension i.e. rounded end of the seal, the smallest cell size chosen was 0.0625 mm. Angle of attack for this simulation was 4.5° . Aim with this setup was to study the flow field in the vicinity of the seal and to identify a possible mechanism for the fluid-structure interaction. Two microphones were placed in the seal vicinity, one above and below the seal. This was done to obtain an estimate of the pressure difference within and outside the flap cove.

Figure 13, shows the location of the microphones placed inside and outside the flap cove.

Besides this, the goal was also to record and provide the surface pressure fluctuations to AIRBUS which would enable them to estimate stiffness of the seal material.

Sound pressure fluctuation contour for the configuration A are show in Figure 12. Contour on the left side depicts the origin and propagation of the acoustic waves, from and in the near- and far-field. Waves originating from the slat, flap cove vicinity and flap trailing edge (T.E.) are clearly distinguishable. Right hand side picture is the zoomed in view of the flap cove area. Only physical phenomenon present in the flap cove vicinity is the Kelvin-Helmholtz (K-H) instability which can be thought of to influence the generation of a FSI response. The wavelength present in the flap cove match the wavelength of the structures in the K-H instability.

Figure 12: Sound pressure fluctuations for F16 configuration A with a rigid seal, -25 to 25 Pa.

Figure 13: Pressure spectra from the microphones above and below the seal, Conf. A.

Figure 13 shows the pressure spectra for the microphones located inside and outside the flap cove. For microphone inside the flap cove, we see a tonal peak at ~ 5 kHz. This resulting tonal feature is specific to the slat noise. The broadband hump present at ~ 2 kHz could have the origin in the flap cove. The frequency of the waves inside the flap cove is in the range of ~ 10 kHz.

Based on this simulation results, the potential mechanism for the fluid-structure mechanism identified is the K-H instability in the flap cove. Frequency range inside the flap cove is ~ 10 kHz for a model scale F16 with a rigid seal. This outcome reveals very small fluctuations on the seal and a potential difficulty to measure the seal vibrations during the deformation measurements. Besides that, internal DLR database suggested that a similar setup with the slat retracted would result in a strong tonal

phenomenon. Considering the above arguments, it was decided to proceed with a configuration with retracted slats.

Configuration B-I

As mentioned in the previous sub-section, based on the internal DLR database and from the simulations performed with both high-lift devices deployed, highlight a necessity to investigate a configuration with retracted slat and keeping the flap as it was. Figure 10, shows the configuration B-I with slat in the retracted position.

Two outcomes were expected from the investigation of this configuration:

1. Setup is similar to the previous findings, of a strong tonal phenomenon, from DLR internal database.
2. Based on the assumption that the K-H instability follows a Strouhal's scaling, slat is retracted to reduce the flow velocities in the vicinity of the seal and is thus attempted to shift the resulting frequency of the tonal features to a low frequency range.

Figure 14, shows the pressure spectra for the microphones inside and outside the flap cove. A strong tonal feature is not observed from the pressure spectra. Broadband humps are seen at several frequencies and they can be traced to the local hydrodynamic structures in the vicinity of the flap cove, specifically near the wing TE.

Figure 14: Pressure spectra from the microphones above and below the seal, Conf. B-I.

Configuration B-II

Figure 11, shows the configuration B-II. This configuration was planned to replicate the full-scale vibration frequency of the seal i.e. to accommodate a bigger wavelength inside the flap cove. To realize this flap was removed, so that a bigger wavelength can fit inside the cove.

Sound pressure fluctuations for the configuration B-II is shown in Figure 15. A distinct tone is observed from the sound pressure contour field, see Figure 16. It appears to originate from the wake behind the wing TE. No interaction with the seal observed. But the frequency at which it is observed is a factor 10 bigger than the full-scale frequency i.e. $\sim 100\text{Hz}$. Difficult to obtain the full-scale frequency with this setup.

Figure 15: Sound pressure fluctuation contour, Conf. B-I.

Figure 16: Pressure spectra from the microphones above and below the seal, Conf. B-II.

3.1.3. Summary and conclusions

It was an attempt to understand the possible mechanism for the FSI response. Kelvin-Helmholtz instability was assumed to be the important physical mechanism for such an interaction. Previous measurement experience for a similar setup, showed a presence of clear tone at a particular frequency. The wavelength of this frequency showed association with the flap cove size. The tone also showed a Strouhal number dependence. It was expected to see a tonal feature around ~1.6 kHz. But in the case of F16 with a rigid seal, and with the setup configurations (A), no noticeable effects i.e. tonal features were observed. Configurations B-I, showed some tonal character in the frequency range of 3 – 5 kHz, but a closer look in the sound pressure field contours revealed the near-field hydrodynamics to be the origin of those peaks. Configuration B-II, depicted a presence of a tone at ~1.5 kHz but it was too big to be accommodated in the effectively elongated flap cove.

Thus, taking into account the success of the experiment i.e. to measure the seal vibration, a bigger flap cove is foreseen. The upcoming section will describe in detail a newly chosen high-lift wing to guarantee a successful FSI experimental database.

3.2. DLR-F15LS-mod

The simulations carried out for the F16 high-lift wing with a rigid seal, showcased a need for the bigger flap cove to accommodate, a closer to the model scale, vibration frequency of the seal. As a result, F15LS high-lift wing with a clean chord length of $c=1.2\text{m}$ was chosen. Figure 17: F15LS experiment in DNW-LLF test facility (EU OPENAIR). It is a 1: ~3.67 model scale wing. Compared to F16, with a $c=0.3\text{m}$, F15LS is a factor four times bigger model. The size of the F15LS had to be reduced as it was too big for the AWB tunnel. This constraint implied the use of wing's modular functionality i.e. only the rear portion of the wing and a flap was used for this investigation.

Figure 17: F15LS experiment in DNW-LLF test facility (EU OPENAIR) and a modular section of F15LS in storage

Figure 18, shows the initial elliptical/draft ellipse nose design. It has a clean chord length of $c=0.63\text{m}$. The flap is deployed at an angle of $\delta_F = 8$ deg with a gap of 15.6 mm and an overlap of 102.8 mm.

Figure 18: Modified F15LS, elliptical/draft ellipse nose.

A mesh refinement study was performed to identify the resolution limits important for the accurate development of the boundary layer. Reynolds number based on the clean chord length was ~2.6 million and Mach number based on the free-stream flow velocity was 0.18. Angle of attack was 0 deg. Computational domain and the numerical setup was similar to that of F16. 3D periodic WMLES slice was used to investigate the modified F15LS wing.

Table 4: Numerical settings for the modified F15LS.

Parameter	Value
Δx_f [m]	1×10^{-3}
Δt [s]	1.68×10^{-6}
Refinement Levels (N)	6
Time [s]	0.57
No. of nodes (in million)	10

Figure 19: Velocity magnitude contour (instantaneous) and Cp-distribution, modified F15LS.

Results shown here are for the coarse setup. This is done to identify the shortcomings of the current nose design. Figure 19: Velocity magnitude contour (instantaneous) and Cp-distribution, modified F15LS. Following observations can be drawn from the velocity contour and the Cp distribution plot:

1. a high flow acceleration on the suction side of the main element, induced by the shape of the nose
2. Further downstream along the wing, a flow separation is present on the suction side starting from the non-dimensional (x/C) of 0.2. Later on, it transitions to a fully turbulent boundary layer
3. Flow on the flap suction side is locally detached which might result in the blockage of the gap flow
4. Flow on the pressure side, immediately before the flap cove, remains attached

Figure 20: Sound pressure fluctuations contour, -25 to 25 Pa, modified F15LS.

Figure 20: Sound pressure fluctuations contour, -25 to 25 Pa, modified F15LS. Separation on the suction side induces additional acoustic disturbance on the suction side of the main element. Based on the observations made above, the new aerodynamic layout of the F15LS geometry with a new nose design had to meet several requirements.

Firstly, the setup of the entire model should keep the flow deflection of the open jet in the wind tunnel in an acceptable range i.e. moderate flow acceleration on the main element and eventually a smaller lift coefficient.

Secondly, the design had to ensure a proper flow-through through the flap cove of the wing with deployed flap for a realistic loading of the flap, which was deemed crucial to properly trigger the on-set of coupled fluid-structure interaction modes. This implies no separation on the flap suction side and an attached flow on the pressure side of the main element.

3.3. Nose design for F15LS modified

Based on the pre-requisites mentioned in the previous sub-section a design space for the new nose was established. The design variations comprise the streamwise length (E) of the nose contour. Furthermore, different camber lines (f) were studied, see Figure 21: Nose design space for the modified F15LS., that induce an effective negative S-shape to lower the suction peak at the leading edge without changing the load on the flap, so that the operation conditions of the flap are maintained while reducing the overall absolute lift. Resulting clean chord length of the modified F15LS is 0.702 m.

Figure 21: Nose design space for the modified F15LS.

Scale resolving aerodynamic flow simulations were conducted on the modified F15LS geometry for different nose designs, see Figure 22: Few variants of the new nose based on the choice of stretching (E) and camber line (f). The pre-experimental simulations made use of a somewhat simplified setup by resolving not the entire wind tunnel setup but restricting the simulation to a slice of limited spanwise extend of $\sim 13\%$ of F15 retracted chord length. The spanwise resolution ensured sufficient resolution of 3-D unsteady turbulent structures at reduced computational effort. Different grids ranging from 36 to 360 million number of grid points have been employed.

Figure 22: Few variants of the new nose based on the choice of stretching (E) and camber line (f)

Figure 23: Comparison of different camber lines (f) for a fixed streamwise length E , modified F15LS. Negative camber reduces the lift without affecting the loading conditions on the flap, but a positive camber increases the suction peak and eventually predicts an overall increase in the lift coefficients. Thus, negative camber line will be the way forward in selection of a new nose.

Figure 23: Comparison of different camber lines (f) for a fixed streamwise length E , modified F15LS.

Combinations of different streamwise length (E) and the camber line (f) along with different angle of attacks were examined to identify a desirable combination that would work the best, given the pre-requisites. Table 5: Design variations of the nose for the modified F15LS. Figure 24: Velocity magnitude (time-averaged) contours along with the C_p distribution for modified F15LS. To reduce the overall lift level without affecting the loading on the flap, different nose configurations underwent a sensitivity test to confirm an attached flow on the pressure side of the main element with reduction in the lift at the leading edge. Results are only shown form the AoA -4.5 deg. Smaller than -4.5 deg the flow was susceptible to separation. Coarser mesh resolution was used here.

Table 5: Design variations of the nose for the modified F15LS.

E	f	AoA [$^{\circ}$]	C_L
1.6	0	-4.5°	0.376
	-0.01	-4.5°	0.3605
	-0.015	-4.5°	0.3599
	-0.02	-4.5°	0.35013
1.8	0	-4.5°	0.3775
	-0.01	-4.5°	0.36889
	-0.015	-4.5°	0.37417
	-0.02	-4.5°	0.35674
2.0	0	-4.5°	0.3875
	-0.01	-4.5°	0.39978
	-0.015	-4.5°	0.39970
	-0.02	-4.5°	0.36594

Figure 24: Velocity magnitude (time-averaged) contours along with the Cp distribution for modified F15LS, different variants of f .

The combination of $f=-0.01$ mm and $E=1.8$, was chosen as an optimal candidate for further investigation as it predicted the smallest lift coefficient with the flow on the pressure side of the main element attached. Streamwise length of 1.8 was chosen as it represents the appropriate extend of the wing for AWB i.e. not too big and not too small. Figure 25 Sound pressure fluctuation for the different variants of f and $E=1.8$. These results of modified F15LS highlight an absence of additional acoustic noise on the suction side as compared to Figure 20.

Figure 25 Sound pressure fluctuation for the different variants of f and $E=1.8$.

F15LS with a new nose configuration i.e. $f=-0.01$ and $E=1.8$, will be used for all further investigations.

3.4. Operating range of mod. F15LS in Wind Tunnel (WT)

With the finally selected nose design the wing's angle of attack (AoA) operating range in the AWB tunnel was tested. To determine the range, we used finer meshes as the focus now is to precisely describe the surface forces.

Until now the 3-D WMLES-LBM simulations were carried out with the free-field flow setup. In such setups the infinite span wing was simulated, realized with periodicity, but in reality, the wing has a finite span which will introduce the flow turning up from the sides of the wing. Additionally, when a wing measured in the AWB will encounter a wind tunnel flow deflection as a reaction to the lift force generated by the wing. All these effects combined will result in the overall smaller lift levels at a given AoA in comparison to the free-field setup.

The process of obtaining the operating range, for the modified F15LS wing, in the WT was to make sure that our chosen nose design will not require higher AoA for generating a moderate lift level. Else given the size of the wing, when inclined at higher AoA, in an open jet facility will impose a major setback in realizing the experiment. It might result in a flow separation on the flap, which will affect the flow in the flap cove and the eventually the hinder the fluid structure phenomenon in the cove.

To identify limits of the operating window, a free-field flow setup was used to compute a lift (C_L) vs. AoA polar as can be seen by the black curve in the Figure 26. The black dots indicate the 3-D WMLES simulations at those AoA. Free-field setups were similar to the ones described in the previous sections. From our internal DLR database, it was known that C_L of 0.7 would result in the massive flow deflection of the jet in the wind tunnel. Thus, it was set as the upper limit for the operating range. Orange box in the Figure 26, demarks the operating range of the modified F15LS in the WT.

Lower limit was obtained from the simulation cases where a flow separation on the pressure side of the wing, near the flap cove, would occur. It was observed to happen at AoA higher than 6 deg, which was later set as a lower operating bound.

Question still remains how to get the effect of the wind tunnel flow deflection?

Figure 26: Operating window for the modified F15LS in the WT

To account for the wind tunnel flow deflection, an idea borrowed from the concept of method of images, which has its origin from the potential flow theory, is applied here. Figure 27: Method of images, Mokhtar. W, PhD, 2006.

Flow deflection is observed in the open jet tunnel when measuring the lifting surfaces/bodies. Numerically this concept was realized in the free-field ProLB setup with the following changes:

1. The domain height was same as the nozzle exit height i.e. 1.2 m
2. Free-field setup uses periodicity only in the spanwise direction, but to realize the flow deflection periodicity was applied at the top and bottom boundaries.

Only constraint with this type of setup is that it does not account for the flow deformation at the boundaries which should result as an effect of an obstacle in the flow i.e. modified F15LS. But it will give us an estimate of the flow deflection effect induced on to the surface forces on the wing i.e. C_L .

Figure 27: Method of images, Mokhtar. W, PhD, 2006.

Figure 28: Velocity magnitude contour (time-averaged), AoA 0 deg. Once the modified F15LS starts to generate lift force, a flow deflection onset is observed. The flow deflection was measured around 8-9 deg from the streamlines shown in the velocity contour. Red curve in the Figure 26 shows the polar for the modified F15LS WT flow deflection effects included. Considerable reduction in the slope of the lift polar is observed in comparison with the free-field lift polar (black curve).

Figure 28: Velocity magnitude contour (time-averaged), AoA 0 deg.

Green curve in the Figure 26, shows the outcome of a full 3-D WT simulation with a nozzle, it will be described in the next sub-section. The outcome of the WT polar is astonishingly closer to the lift polar obtained from the open jet wind tunnel flow deflection setup (red curve). This comparison highlights that the effect of the tip vortices from a finite span wing is not at all significant for this case. It also emphasizes that a simple open jet wind tunnel flow deflection setup is able to very closely predict the lift slopes for the full 3-D WT simulations.

The operating window limit was apriorly set to -3 to +3 deg. Measurements were later successfully carried out within these operating bounds i.e. modified F15LS obeyed all the defined pre-requisites.

In total more than fifty 3-D WMLES-LBM simulations have been performed for the design setups (discussed in sub-sections 3.3 and 3.4).

3.5. Proof of concept 3-D WT simulations

As a final step in the numerical design study, 3-D WT simulations of the modified F15LS under wind tunnel installation conditions were carried out to confirm the desired performance of the modified aerodynamic layout for the targeted angle of attack range of the wing. The simulation resolves the full spanwise extent (2.1m) of the model together with the wind tunnel nozzle and accounts for the wind tunnel free shear layers and resulting wind tunnel flow deflection. In total, 20 different full wind tunnel setups were simulated.

Simulated flow velocity was 40 m/s at the nozzle exit plane. AoA for the WT simulations was 0 deg. Different variations with the numerical WT setup were carried out to determine a few decisive parameters for the WT test definition.

1. Position of the wing from the nozzle exit plane?
2. Requirement of the boundary layer fences?
3. Seal installation angle?
4. Flow deflection angle

Figure 29, shows the time-averaged velocity magnitude contours for the WT simulation where the wing is placed 0.3 m away from the nozzle exit. This test was performed to identify how far the wing should be placed. When the wing is closer to the nozzle exit plane, a massive flow deformation, as can be seen from the streamlines, along the wall normal direction (z-axis) is observed. Later on a distance of 0.5 m was found to be sufficient enough with respect to the flow deformation and also avoiding interaction with the downstream converging nozzle shear layers.

Figure 29: Initial position of the modified F15LS wing placed 0.3 m away from the nozzle exit plane.

Since there will be a massive interaction of the nozzle shear layers with the wing, as can be identified from the arrangement in Figure 29, it was decided to test if a boundary layer fence is required to safeguard the central portion of the wing. As a preliminary formulation, boundary layer fences were designed based on the handbook formulas, see Figure 31. Boundary layer fences were placed 0.35m away, on either side of the mid span plane.

Comparison between the C_p distribution of modified F15LS with and without fence is shown in Figure 30. In the middle portion of the wing the contours of C_p appear to be uniform along the span, almost similar, for both the cases. Thus, advocating against the requirement of a b. layer fence. Figure 32, showcases the streamlines in the flap cove for with and without b. layer fence. From the spacing between the

streamlines, it can be identified that without fences there is spanwise component of the flow present. This is a result of the flow entrainment from both the open ends of the flap cove. But a decisive factor in this case is to have a 2-D flow in the flap cove and it can only be guaranteed with the boundary layer fences covering the flap cove from either side. This criterion emphasized a strict requirement of b. layer fences.

Figure 30: Top-view of the wing with Cp distribution contours for w/o and with fence.

Figure 31: Preliminary design of the boundary layer fence, 3 mm thick.

Figure 32: Streamlines in the flap cove for without and with boundary layer fence, velocity magnitude contours (time-avg.)

With the help of these streamline plots, see Figure 32 with fence, it was jointly agreed to have the seal installed at an angle of 3 deg from a reference horizontal plane.

Contours depicted in Figure 33 are the outcome of a final WT setup with b. layer fences along with the other identified key parameters discussed before. Moderate flow deflection is seen from the streamlines plotted in the Figure 33, left picture. Flow separation was absent for both the wing and the flap. This guarantees a correct loading on the flap. Flow deflection when measured from the streamlines is similar to the one obtained from the open-jet wind tunnel flow deflection simulations i.e. 8 – 9 deg. This highlights the modified F15LS under the WT installation condition also satisfies the criteria laid out for the design beforehand.

Figure 33: Proof of concept full 3-D WT simulation, Velocity magnitude contours (time-averaged).

A comparison between the C_p from an open-jet wind tunnel flow deflection simulation, computed pre-measurement, and the C_p measured in WT campaign is shown in Figure 34.

Figure 34 Comparison of the pre-test simulated C_p distribution with the measured C_p distribution.

Few observations from the measured C_p :

1. Moderate suction peaks on the leading edge of the main element i.e. moderate lift levels
2. attached flow on the pressure side of the main element that will guarantee the proper flap loading.
3. Flow on the flap also appears to be attached.

This is a very preliminary comparison meant to showcase that the wing with a modified aerodynamic layout delivers the same behavior in the measurements as it was predicted by the pre-measurement simulations.

3.6. Summary and Outlook

Goal of the numerical design study was to support the setup of the wind tunnel experiment. Numerical studies were carried out with 3-D scale resolving unsteady Large-Eddy Simulation (LES) with the Lattice Boltzmann Method (LBM). Simulation software used was LaBS/ProLB. The simulations realized a “one-way” prediction solely based on non-flexible rigid geometry description.

Outcome:

The main characteristics observed during the experimental test have confirmed the before-test WMLES-LBM evaluation of critical performance characteristics of the high-lift wing design, including angle of attack requirements, proper operation of the flap, and flow deflection by the wing.

Outlook:

Next steps will involve a systematic a-posteriori validation of the ProLB results with the measurements based on the slightly modified flap settings eventually selected and used in the experiment.

4. Test setup

4.1. Test facility

The Aeroacoustic Wind tunnel Braunschweig (AWB) is a research facility for the Technical Acoustics department of the German Aerospace center (DLR) in Braunschweig/Northern Germany.

The closed-circuit tunnel (Figure 35) has an open test section with a 0.8 m x 1.2 m nozzle (width ΔY x height ΔZ). Flow velocities up to 63 m/s are possible. The wind tunnel flow passes through a semi-anechoic measurement room (test section $\Delta X=3.64\text{m}$) which is characterized by a lower cut-off frequency of about 200 Hz for broadband noise. An adaptive collector can be adjusted to account for any flow deflections that are induced by high-lift systems. The distance between the ground and collector inlet is $\Delta Z=610\text{mm}$ (Figure 36).

Figure 35: AWB wind tunnel test facility

Figure 36: Open test section of the AWB wind tunnel test facility

The most important non-moving geometric references w.r.t. AWB-coordinates are listed in Table 6. All PIV-Test related system are also fixed w.r.t. AWB.

Table 6: Crucial geometric references which are fixed in AWB

	X [mm]	Y [mm]	Z [mm]	Comment
Model turning axis	837.502	--	39.094	
Out-of-flow Mic	548.636	-280.356	-937.863	
Acoustic Meas. Reference Point	986.024	0	- 15.426	for $\alpha_{geo}=+1^\circ$ and $L=80\text{mm}$
Hot wire reference point	884.073	-654	-171.218	$\alpha_{geo}=+1^\circ$, no seal

4.2. Wing Model

The DLR-F15LSmod is a 2D wind tunnel model of a transport aircraft wing section. It is designed for use in low speed wind tunnels up to Mach 0.18 for atmospheric conditions.

It consists of the following products (see Figure 37):

- Wing model product groups
 - wing nose
 - alpha adjustment unit
 - flap brackets for positioning of flap relative to wing
 - Boundary layer fence
- Seal holder unit
- Wing model instrumentation
 - Surface pressure sensors
 - Pressure tabs

Figure 37: Wing model and product groups

4.2.1. Model axes and positioning in AWB

Via its alpha adjustment unit, the model is connected to a rig of X95 structural rails (Figure 38). The wing leading edge is positioned with a distance of $\Delta X \sim 500\text{mm}$ to the wind tunnel nozzle exit at $\alpha_{\text{geo}} = 0^\circ$.

The X95 support rests on a lifting table. While the lifting table height was adjusted during the initial rigging it remained fixed until the end of the test campaign.

Figure 38: Wing support and positioning in AWB during the initial rigging.

The model turning axis (see Figure 36 and Figure 38Figure 37) is the mechanical reference between model and AWB coordinates. It is located at $X=837.502\text{mm}$; $Z=39.094\text{mm}$ (in AWB coordinates).

Model turning point coordinates are fixed to the main wing's point of rotation. They do not change with adjustment of the model incidence α_{geo} . However, they are not the official model reference coordinates and play only an auxiliary role when transforming to AWB coordinates. Crucial model reference points w.r.t. the turning axis are displayed in Figure 39 and listed in Table 7.

Figure 39: model reference axes and auxiliary reference systems

Table 7: Crucial model reference points in turning point coordinates

Ref. Point	X _t [mm]	Z _t [mm]	Comment
WLEref	-317.026	-5.006	origin of the main <u>w</u> ing element, for displaying Cp pressure distribution. The origin of x is the <u>l</u> eading <u>e</u> dge of the non-inclined wing.
WTE1	259.119	3.625	Auxiliary reference which can be easily selected in CAD. It refers to the <u>t</u> railing <u>e</u> dge on the upper/suction side (1), not on the lower/pressure side (2).
Seal	69.534	-56.11	Seal installation reference point located on the flap pressure side (not: the flap cove side); direction: inclined by $\alpha_{seal}=+3^\circ$
Seal_TE (L=80mm)	149.424	-51.923	For calculation of an acoustic measurement reference point, depends on seal length L, inclination of the seal holder $\alpha_{seal}=3^\circ$ must be considered
at flap setting #7:			
FLEref	168.43	-66.29	origin of the undeflected flap <u>l</u> eading <u>e</u> dge, i.e. at $\delta_F=0^\circ$, for displaying Cp pressure distributions, same position as flap pressure tap #30. The flap deflection angle must be considered for transformations.
FTE1	503.845	-93.977	auxiliary reference on $\delta_F=8^\circ$ (!) deflected <u>f</u> lap (constant δ_F during FALCON test), refers to the <u>t</u> railing <u>e</u> dge on the upper/suction side (1) of the flap

4.2.2. Alpha adjustment unit

The model turning axis is strongly related to the alpha-adjustment unit. This unit allows to adjust the geometrical incidence within a range of $\pm 15^\circ$ via a cylindrical elongated hole (Figure 40).

Open test section experiments especially with high-lift wings cause a wind tunnel flow deflection and hence a mismatch between the geometrical incidence and the physical angle of attack. In order to be able to cross-compare open test section experiments with rigid wall boundary conditions (e.g. in most numerical simulations), the pressure distribution e.g. of a simulated undeflected flow is matched by adjusting the geometric incidence in the experiment.

The test range used in FALCON is $\alpha_{\text{geo}} = -3^\circ \dots +3^\circ$ in steps of $\Delta\alpha_{\text{geo}} = 1^\circ$.

The main test with various seals and PIV instrumentation was conducted with $\alpha_{\text{geo}} = +1^\circ$.

The model's existing transportation boreholes were equipped with a bearing shaft. An SKF deep groove ball bearing allows for smooth rotation of the wing model. On the X95-support side, a clamping plate is mounted. This plate (as well as the bearing cap) holds the outer side of the SKF bearing and also contains the cylindrical elongated hole (Figure 40). The geometric incidence position is clamped via a screw connection.

Figure 40: Parts of the alpha adjustment unit, starboard side.

The starboard side alpha adjustment unit contains the mirrored parts of the portside unit, and also an additional spacer plate. The parts were designed by DLR and manufactured by DLR and Meviy Misumi.

4.2.3. Wing with a large flap cove

A geometrically large flap cove was deemed suitable for the FALCON experiments. Hence, the flap-cove defining model parts from a very large model, the DLR-F15LS, were selected. F15LS is a wing of scale $\sim 1:3.67$, with a clean chord length of $c=1200\text{mm}$ (Figure 41).

Figure 41: F15LS model. On the starboard side: selected flap cove defining parts for the FALCON test and size comparison to the AWB nozzle.

F15LS is too large for testing in a mid-to-small test facility. Therefore, DLR designed a new wing nose for Falcon (see sections 3.2 and 3.3). The requirements for the geometric contour are: low lift on the main wing while retaining the characteristic flow properties near the flap cove and further downstream.

The wing nose initially received an elliptical draft contour (dotted lines in Figure 42) which fits to the adjoining main wing trailing edge part. The upstream located half-ellipsoid nose contour (area ratio $X/Z = 0.66$) was then replaced with a two-parameter contour model (parameters E and f , see section 3.3). The wing aerodynamics design and concept proof was conducted with the help of numerical tools, such as the 2D flow solver FLOW3R, Xfoil and ProLB. Based on the simulations, the parameters $\varepsilon=1.8$ and $f=0.01$ were selected for the construction design.

As a result of the comprehensive design studies by DLR, the F15LS clean chord length was shortened from $c=1200\text{mm}$ to $c=700.8\text{mm}$ for the F15LSmod. The two individual airfoil elements have a clean chord length of $c=576\text{mm}$ for the main wing and $c=336.5\text{mm}$ for the flap (Figure 42).

Figure 42: FALCON F15LSmod, clean chord model geometry and axis reference systems. Dotted lines indicate the draft contour.

The missing wing nose part was milled out of polyurethane modeling material and painted in black matte color with heat resistant paint ($T_{\max}=660^{\circ}\text{C}$) by Airbus Spain in Getafe (Figure 43).

Figure 43: Manufacturing and painting of wing nose. Photos by Luis Javier Nieto García, Airbus Getafe

4.2.4. Flap brackets

Flap brackets are the means to position the flap relative to the main wing. They allow to manipulate the geometry of the flap cove and its flow conditions.

The F15LS features the possibility to mount flap brackets either over-wing (for one fixed flap position) or under-wing. The under-wing flap bracket set consists out of 4 parts which allow to adjust the flap deflection angle δ_F , Overlap and Gap (in this order).

Figure 44: Falcon flap brackets

In order to be able to test the Falcon flap settings, two parts of each existing F15LS flap bracket set needed to be redesigned. While the selected F15LS parts consist of three slots for the flap holders (see Figure 41), Falcon used only the two sets which are not compromised by any wind tunnel flow.

The Falcon model needed a flap bracket design on the portside. A portside flap bracket set with 4 parts was designed: It provides optical access while also matching the same flap bracket adjustment measures and the flap rotation point.

The flap deflection angle can be adjusted via pin to either $\delta_F = 8^\circ$ or 14° .

The flap deflection angle was fixed to $\delta_F = 8^\circ$ during the test campaign.

The Overlap value is the more horizontal flap adjustment parameter. It is determined by clamping Johansson gauge blocks in the horizontal flap bracket and fixing the screw of the horizontal elongated hole. The adjustment range is 45mm, i.e. $\pm 22.5\text{mm}$ w.r.t. to flap setting 1.

The Gap parameter is the more vertical flap parameter. It was adjusted by clamping Johansson gauge blocks between main wing trailing edge and flap (i.e. the actual Gap position) and fixing the position via screws in the vertical elongated holes. The vertical adjustment range is $\Delta=30\text{mm}$, allowing an adjustment of $\pm 15\text{mm}$ w.r.t. to flap setting 1.

Table 8: Falcon flap settings

Flap Setting	Bracket Values		Real Values		FTE1 Position		Duct props (at rest)	
	Vertical* (~Gap)	Horizontal (~OvL)	Gap	OvL	X _{WLE} [mm]	Z _{WLE} [mm]	OvL-Seal	Inlet/Outlet
1	17	34.738	15.2	102.8	808.766	-73.885	6.785	45%
2	17	57	14.456	80.584	831.028	-73.885	29.011	201%
3	17.591	43.133	15.2	95.451	817.161	-74.476	15.2	100%
4	17.372	39.338	15.2	98.246	813.366	-74.257	11.4	75%
5	31.736	46.843	29.2	90.741	820.871	-88.621	22.192	76%
6	24.611	43.399	22.2	94.185	817.427	-81.496	16.65	75%
7	32.086	46.843	29.55	90.741	819.987	-93.42	22.325	76%

* not used for adjusting, Gap was directly measured

Flap settings 1-6 (see Table 8) were tested during the Aero test and flap setting 5 down-selected for the main test. The PIV BL fence (initially for the main wing element only) needed to be adapted to feature the correct flap contour. This was done mid test with standard tools. The realized Gap after installation was measured to have an offset of only 0.35mm to target and was labelled as flap setting 7.

The main test with PIV instrumentation was conducted with flap setting 7, i.e. Flap $\delta_F = 8^\circ$, Gap = 29.55mm and OvL = 90.741mm.

4.2.5. Tripping

Flow turbulators are a very useful tool when testing models of small scale. In order to make the tests comparable to e.g. to full size models, tripping is used to help turn a laminar boundary layer into a turbulent boundary layer.

Based on the numerical results, DLR decided to omit tripping on the main wing and the flap pressure side, but to use tripping on the flap suction side and in between the boundary layer fences.

Figure 45: Boundary conditions for applying tripping and finalized positions

The tripping installation requirements are to install upstream of the GRAS-Array (1&3, i.e. upstream of flap pressure tap #21) as well as to install in between the pressure taps (Figure 45).

Two locations have been tested (Table 9):

1. The first test (data points 119-134) was conducted with 0.205mm thick Streifeneder zig-zag turbulators. The tripping is located at $x/c_{flap} \sim 12\%$, in between flap pressure taps #23 and #21. The tripping has been applied mid test, with the difficulty of the flap being mounted and the corresponding limited vision.

The recorded data of the GRAS sensors was analysed by Nan Hu and Arnaud Le Floch w.r.t. the spectral shape. They found [mail from 17.06.2025, 21:35] that the tripping does significantly reduce the sensor-installation-related disturbance. However, they also argued that the zig-zag tripping might be installed too close to the sensors, since the tripping-induced turbulence structure significantly affects the measured coherence.

This analysis agrees with the working mechanism of zig-zag tripping: Zig-Zag tape will merely prepare the boundary layer for transition, so laminar flow continues for a few percent downstream until the local pressure gradient does the tripping. It makes sense that the close GRAS sensors 1&3 may be affected by too close tripping while sensors 2 and 4 deliver the expected spectral shapes.

Hence, the second tripping was moved further upstream to $x/c_{flap} \sim 5\%$, in between the pressure taps #25 and #23.

- The second tripping was used during the main test (data points 227-380). It was costum-made by contouring double-layered matte black Gaffa AT205 tape with pinking scissors in order to meet PIV requirements.

Table 9: Use of 3D Turbulators

	#1 Streifeneder Zig-zag	#2 Self-produced PIV zig-zag				
Geometry						
Affected data points	119-134	227-380 (end)				
thickness	0.205mm	~0.180mm				
color	transparent	matte black				
Photo						
position	flap suction side					
	upstream	mid	downstr.	upstream	mid	downstr.
x-position [mm]	29.9	35.9	41.9	11.1	14.5	17.9
x/c_{flap} [-]	8.9%	10.7%	12.4%	3.3%	4.3%	5.3%
adjoining pressure port	23	...	21	25	...	23

4.2.6. Boundary Layer Fence

The numerical test support started the initial BL fence design by determining offsets from the wing contour based on literature. The design was numerically simulated and an evaluation was made whether the boundary layer fences could be left out. Even though the flow analysis looks promising without any boundary layer tests, it was decided to test with boundary layer fences.

Figure 46: Contours of Boundary Layer fence #1

The initial rectangular design with rounded edges (1 in Figure 46) was manufactured with a more aerodynamic nose. Furthermore, the trailing edge received serrations based on the approximated boundary layer thickness. Contours were slightly adapted for manufacturing to machine the wing contours with the Ø1mm milling tool. The boundary layer fence is made out of 5mm thick Makrolon®, i.e. a polycarbonate.

During the test, the manufactured boundary layer fence had to be shortened for high speed testing, i.e. at wind tunnel speeds higher than 40m/s. The need to detach the flap and hence the boundary layer fence from the mounted main wing caused to split the boundary layer fence in two parts, the nose section and the flap-fixed section.

The boundary layer fence was installed to allow free movement of the seal (b=600mm). The distance of $\Delta Y=610\text{mm}$ between the two boundary layer fences allows for a symmetrical clearance of 5mm to the seal edge.

Two opposing design requirements made the manufacturing of two different boundary layer fences necessary (see Table 10).

Table 10: Opposing design requirements for the Boundary layer fences

Critical design requirement	AERO BL fence	PIV BL fence
Optical access from flap cove on wing portside Black matte background on wing starboard side	Limited access by too much tape in flap cove	Good optical access
Adjustable flap position	Good adjustment	Flap setting #7 only
Manufacturing design		
#serrations	6	7

The PIV BL fence was initially designed for the main test w/o the flap and later adapted to contain flap setting #7 (Figure 47).

(#1) "AERO BL fence"
adjustable flap position
 $\delta_F = 0^\circ \dots 18^\circ$, full range of Gap/OvL brackets

PIV-BL fences
suitable optical access in flap cove
(#2) for main wing w/o flap

re-purposed

(#3) for 2-element wing
w/fixed flap position

Figure 47: Boundary layer fences

4.3. TC2 Wing flap cove seal model

Since the existing main wing part did not contain a seal adapter interface, the FALCON seal adapter interface of length 15x25.5 (height x length) was added to the existing F15LS contour. While the original clean-chord F15LS contour is inclined by 10° in the flap cove, the FALCON seal adapter is inclined by only 3° (Figure 48). This change allows to test a greater parameter space, especially configurations where the seal is about to smoothly encompass the approaching flap during its closing process. The design change is encouraged by an analysis of the streamlines in the vicinity of the flap cove.

Figure 48: Original flap cove vs. FALCON flap cove

4.3.1. Seal as a test parameter

14 seals were manufactured for testing. The tested seals can be differentiated in three different groups (Figure 49):

- Blank steel seals for the aero test
- L=80mm PIV steel seals for the main test
- L=50mm multi-material seals for the main test, mainly w/ PIV (Figure 51)

All main test seals contain a dot pattern which was designed by DLR Göttingen to meet the required resolution of the seal movement. The dot pattern is necessary for the 3D dynamic seal surface measurements with IPCT (see section 4.4.7).

The PIV steel seals were coated via silk screen printing by the company DieSignMaker (white dots on black background). The rubber seals contain black dots on white/light grey background. They were spray coated during the test campaign with the same dot pattern by means of a stencil (see also Table 11).

Characteristic material properties were determined in separate tests (see sections below, summary in Table 11). The seal geometry is portrayed in Figure 50 and Figure 51.

Figure 49: FALCON test seals

Figure 50: Geometry of the seals

Figure 51: Multi material seals of Length L=50mm

Seal mass of the unclamped/free length

The seal mass was determined on 23.07.2025 (Figure 52) with help of a scale (measurement range 0...600g with a display uncertainty of ± 0.1 g). The **mass of the free/unclamped length** was estimated by determining the ratio between clamped and unclamped volume. This was only possible by determining missing material in the clearance holes and pockets (Figure 53) with the help of CAD, a steel ruler (0...1000mm ± 0.5 mm) for the span width, a caliper [0...150mm ± 0.05 mm] and an outside micrometer (0...25mm ± 0.005 mm).

The uncertainty accounts for manufacturing accuracy as well as the clearance fit between screw diameter and clearance hole diameter.

The determined unclamped seal mass (Table 11) is good within 1% based on Gaussian propagation of uncertainty.

As a backup check, the density of the bulk material was determined. For the PIV steel sealings, the coating had to be considered. This was only possible with a high uncertainty. However, the calculated densities fall short of the reported values.

All seal tapes (Figure 52), i.e. including the ones on the rigid part of the seal, were determined to have a mass of less than 0.05g.

Figure 52: Mass determination of seal and tapes

Figure 53: Estimation of free length of seal

Table 11: Seal mass test by DLR from 23.07.2025

Seal ID	[-]	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Name	[-]	Bl.St L80 t0.2	Bl.St L80 t0.1	Bl.St L50 t0.15	Bl.St L20 t0.2	PIV.St L80 t0.5	PIV.St L50 t0.5	PIV.St L80 t0.2	PIV.St L50 t0.2	PIV.St L80 t0.1	PIV.St L50 t0.1	TPU L50 t6	Airbus L50 t3.6
Thickness, Core Material	[mm]	t0.2	t0.1	t0.15	t0.2	t0.5	t0.5	t0.2	t0.2	t0.1	t0.1	t6	t4.677
Core Material	[-]	blank Steel				PIV Steel						TPU	Rubber
Supplier	[-]	Metalstore24				Metalstore24		Deharde				DasFilament	Airbus
material specifics	[-]	rolled				rolled		sheet				dove-tail fit + glue	composi
Coating supplier	[-]	--				Die SignMaker						DLR-Go stencil & spray-coat. / pen	
Free Length	[mm]	L80	L80	L50	L20	L80	L50	L80	L50	L80	L50	L50	L50
	Δabs.	±0.5	±0.5	±0.5	±0.5	±0.5	±0.5	±0.2	±0.2	±0.2	±0.2	±0.1	±0.1
	Δrel.	0.6%	0.6%	1.0%	2.5%	0.6%	1.0%	0.3%	0.4%	0.3%	0.4%	0.1%	0.1%
Width	[mm]	600	600	600	600	600	600	600	600	600	600	598	600
	Δabs.	±0.1	±0.1	±0.1	±0.1	±0.1	±0.1	±0.1	±0.1	±0.1	±0.1	±0.1	±0.1
	Δrel.	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
unclamped surface area	[mm ²]	48000	48000	30000	12000	48000	30000	48000	30000	48000	30000	29800	30000
	Δabs.	±300.0	±300.0	±300.0	±300.0	±300.0	±300.0	±120.1	±120.0	±120.1	±120.0	±30.0	±30.1
	Δrel.	0.6%	0.6%	1.0%	2.5%	0.6%	1.0%	0.3%	0.4%	0.3%	0.4%	0.1%	0.1%
full surface area of part	[mm ²]	56370	56370	38370	20370	56370	38370	56370	38370	56370	38370	38170	38370
	Δabs.	±51.5	±51.5	±51.5	±51.5	±51.5	±51.5	±51.5	±51.5	±51.5	±51.5		
	Δrel.	0.1%	0.1%	0.1%	0.3%	0.1%	0.1%	0.1%	0.1%	0.1%	0.1%		
unclamped volume	[cm ³]											178	140
	Δabs.											±1.5	±1.5
	Δrel.											0.8%	1.1%
full volume of part	[cm ³]											212	174
	Δabs.											±0.0	±0.0
	Δrel.											0.0%	0.0%
part mass, meas.	[g]	89.0	42.6	44.5	31.2	219.4	148.0	86.8	59.3	44.5	30.0	242.3	212.8
unclamped/full part	Vol%	0.852	0.852	0.782	0.589	0.852	0.782	0.852	0.782	0.852	0.782	0.840	0.805
	Δabs.	±0.005	±0.005	±0.008	±0.015	±0.005	±0.008	±0.002	±0.003	±0.002	±0.003	±0.007	±0.009
	Δrel.	0.6%	0.6%	1.0%	2.5%	0.6%	1.0%	0.3%	0.4%	0.3%	0.4%	0.8%	1.1%
seal mass, free length	[g]	75.8	36.3	34.8	18.4	186.8	115.7	73.9	46.4	37.9	23.5	203.5	171.3
	Δabs.	±0.5	±0.2	±0.4	±0.5	±0.1	±1.2	±0.2	±0.2	±0.1	±0.1	±1.7	±1.8
	Δrel.	0.6%	0.7%	1.0%	2.5%	0.6%	1.0%	0.3%	0.5%	0.3%	0.5%	0.8%	1.1%
thickness	[mm]	0.20	0.10	0.15	0.20	0.52	0.52	0.21	0.21	0.12	0.12	5.98	4.68

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Seal ID	[-]	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Name	[-]	Bl.St L80 t0.2	Bl.St L80 t0.1	Bl.St L50 t0.15	Bl.St L20 t0.2	PIV.St L80 t0.5	PIV.St L50 t0.5	PIV.St L80 t0.2	PIV.St L50 t0.2	PIV.St L80 t0.1	PIV.St L50 t0.1	TPU L50 t6	Airbus L50 t3.6
	Δabs.	±0.005	±0.005	±0.005	±0.005	±0.005	±0.005	±0.005	±0.005	±0.005	±0.005	±0.050	±0.050
	Δrel.	2.5%	5.0%	3.3%	2.5%	1.0%	1.0%	2.4%	2.4%	4.3%	4.3%	0.1%	0.1%
(mixed) density calculated	[kg/ m³]	7894	7557	7732	7658	7485	7418	7333	7359	6865	6799	1142	1221
	Δabs.	±203.8	±381.3	±269.8	±272.6	±86.2	±103.5	±175.9	±178.4	±299.4	±297.9	±9.7	±13.2
	Δrel.	2.6%	5.0%	3.5%	3.6%	1.2%	1.4%	2.4%	2.4%	4.4%	4.4%	0.8%	1.1%
#dot-printed sides	[-]	0	0	0	0	2	2	1	1	1	1	0	0
Method 1 mass of dot- printing	[g]					3	2	2	1	2	1		
	Δabs.					±0.2	±0.1	±0.1	±0.1	±0.1	±0.1		
	Δrel.					5.4%	5.5%	5.4%	5.4%	5.4%	5.4%		
Coating thickness	[mm]					0	0	0	0	0	0		
	Δabs.					±0.0	±0.0	±0.0	±0.0	±0.0	±0.0		
	Δrel.					25.0%	25.0%	50.0%	50.0%	33.3%	33.3%		
Method 2 mass of dot- printing	[g]					2	1	1	1	2	1		
	Δabs.					±0.9	±0.5	±0.6	±0.4	±0.7	±0.5		
	Δrel.					41.7%	41.7%	60.1%	60.1%	47.1%	47.1%		
1&2] mass of dot-printing	[g]					3	2	1	1	2	1		
	Δabs.					±1.4	±0.9	±0.9	±0.6	±0.7	±0.5		
	Δrel.					53.3%	53.3%	68.1%	68.1%	47.1%	47.1%		
mass of core material	[g]					184	114	73	46	36	22		
	Δabs.					±1.5	±2.0	±1.1	±0.8	±0.9	±0.6		
	Δrel.					0.8%	1.8%	1.5%	1.7%	2.4%	2.6%		
density of core material, calculated	[kg/ m³]					7675	7605	7562	7591	7566	7490		
	Δabs.					±108.0	±172.4	±214.7	±223.7	±376.5	±381.7		
	Δrel.					1.4%	2.3%	2.8%	2.9%	5.0%	5.1%		
Density, supplier sheet	[kg/ m³]	7850	7850	7850	7850	7850	7850	7850	7850	7850	7850	1230	
Young's modulus	E [MPa]	185e3	185e3	185e3	185e3	185e3	185e3	185e3	185e3	185e3	185e3	200... 250	3.3 ...5.2
Poisson's ratio	ν [-]	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.5	~0.5

Static load test for Airbus rubber seal

The table below table provides the stiffness in bending from specific Falcon static tests performed on the rubber seal in Airbus facilities (Figure 54 and Table 12).

Figure 54: Rubber seal static load tests clamped in nominal AWB tunnel conditions.

Table 12: Estimation of Bending stiffness for Rubber seal.

BENDING STIFFNESS ESTIMATION FROM <u>STATIC LOAD TESTS</u>		Roark's Formulas for Stress and Strain		
Applied Static Load	Measured deflection	$D = \beta \cdot P \cdot a^2 / \delta$	Bending Stiffness $E = 12 \cdot D \cdot (1 - \nu^2) / h^3$	Bending Stiffness
F [N]	δ [m]	D [Nm]	[N/m ²]	[MPa]
3.096	0.00491	0.0088	2.94E+06	2.94
4.042	0.00582	0.0097	3.24E+06	3.24
7.460	0.00954	0.0109	3.65E+06	3.65
		mean:	3.28E+06	3.28*
		mean:	5.17E+06	5.17**

$\beta = 0.0056$ for square clamped plate

* Stiffness in bending related to squared rubber seal deformed state as per static tests

** Stiffness in bending related to rubber seal deformed state as per static tests assuming infinite long seal.

Free edge bending test for Airbus rubber seal

Three additional static tests were performed: a free edge test (see Figure 55, Figure 56 and Table 13), a pure torsional test (Table 14 and Figure 55) of the rubber seal span wise section as per below photos and tables:

Figure 55: Measurement of free edge displacement with a caliper

Figure 56: Sketch of the free edge bending test

Table 13: Estimation of Stiffness in Free edge Bending for Rubber seal

Free edge applied static load	Measured free edge displacement δ [m]	Stiffness E $E = P \cdot L^3 / (3 \cdot I \cdot \delta)$ E [MPa]
P [N]		
1.833	0.00636	5.34
2.080	0.00741	5.20
3.096	0.0121	4.74
4.042	0.01542	4.85
5.372	0.01748	5.69
7.460	0.02115	6.53
	Mean E:	5.39
Seal chord L	0.050 [m]	
$I = b \cdot h^3 / 12$	$2.25 \cdot 10^{-9}$ [m ⁴]	
Seal thickn. h	0.003 [m]	

Table 14: Estimation of Torsional Stiffness for Rubber seal

Free edge applied static load	displacement	Torsional Stiffness $GJ=(P \cdot d) \cdot L / (2\delta/b)$
P [N]	δ [m]	Nm ²
3.096	0.00021	0.921
4.042	0.00045	0.561
7.460	0.00098	0.476
	Mean:	0.653
L: Length of the plate	0.05	[m]
b: width of the plate	0.05	[m]
d: level arm	0.05	[m]

Figure 57: Measurement of Torsional Stiffness

4.3.2. Seal holder for sheet metal

The 15x25.5 design space is split into an interface bar of 15x10 and an adapter bar (Figure 58). The seal is fixed with 16x M4 ultra low flat head screws to the adapter bar and clamps the seal at the edge of the bar.

Figure 58: Seal interface for sheet metal seals

There are contour smoothing pieces which allow for a smooth and continuous flap cove geometry despite the addition of the seal holder. The pieces contain cable channels for the main wing mounted surface sensors #5 and #6. The parts were mainly 3D printed by DLR and are made of the material GreenTEC Pro black which is distributed by the company Extrudr. An exception is the PIV Steel insert which was produced by DLR using wire electric discharge machining (wire EDM).

4.3.3. Seal holder for rubber seals

The seal holder for rubber seal is based on the specs of the supplied Airbus HTP seal, especially the maximum thickness of 6mm.

The 15x25.5 design space is split into an interface bar of 15x19.5 and the seal with a max. thickness of 6mm and a 15x3 washer bar with blind holes for M5 ultra low flat head screws. Two 15x3 washer bars were made, one with 13 blind holes for the original Airbus rubber sealing (clamping at center position) and another with an alternative spacing of 14 blind holes (clamping of the edge of the bar).

A shorter set of the contouring pieces allows to install the Airbus seal and TPU-seal with their 20x3 pockets w/o the need to shorten towards 15x3.

4.4. Instrumentation

4.4.1. Wing Aerodynamics

The model is equipped with one pressure tap section at $Y=-195\text{mm}$ (Figure 59), consisting of 32 taps on the main wing (Table 15) and 21 taps on the flap (Table 16). The taps are connected to $\Delta p = 5 \text{ PSI}$ (0.34 bar) pressure scanners, either directly via tubing or with pressure couplings. The pressure scanners are organized in two groups of 32.

DLR checked the instrumentation in the pre-test.

The following points are especially relevant for the processing from Online to Offline data:

- It is recommended to exclude pressure tap #70 in the evaluation. This tap was often closed by the seal tape.
- Data points 1 to 56 do not contain the measurement of DP_AMB, which is the offset between the static pressure in the wind tunnel and the adjacent test preparation room where the ambient pressure P_{AMB} is determined. DP_AMB was placed on the 32nd channel of the first pressure scanner.
- Data points 135-226 were tested without the flap.

Figure 59: Pressure Tabs with their corresponding Tap number

Table 15: Main wing Pressure Tap Coordinates in wing leading edge coordinates

Section	Part	Element	Side	Tap	x [mm]	z [mm]
22	2	TE	Up	01	576.041	8.436
				03	549.296	14.663
				05	522.594	20.068
				07	463.254	30.738
				09	361.388	44.611
				11	222.932	55.963
		LE		21	171.990	58.394
				22	142.994	58.451
				23	117.896	56.936
				24	94.704	54.311
				25	75.166	50.968
				26	61.252	47.768
				27	51.000	44.839
				28	40.107	41.023

				29	28.951	36.056
				30	18.258	29.681
				31	9.117	21.761
				32	0.922	7.354
				33	0.187	-3.168
			Low	34	1.231	-8.442
				35	3.112	-13.613
				36	5.720	-18.615
				37	8.935	-23.395
				38	16.708	-32.157
				39	30.208	-43.137
				40	48.777	-54.046
				41	70.103	-63.147
				42	91.908	-69.848
				43	113.143	-74.371
		TE	44	134.058	-77.222	
			45	158.568	-78.476	
			46	190.393	-76.314	
			67	279.304	-65.850	
			70	361.388	-53.089	

Table 16: Flap Pressure Tap Coordinates in flap leading edge reference coordinates (undeflected)

Section	Part	Element	Side	Tap	x [mm]	z [mm]
22	3	flap	up	01	336.000	17.254
				03	302.400	26.202
				05	268.800	33.372
				08	215.040	45.326
				10	201.600	47.040
				12	156.794	51.272
				14	134.400	52.552
				17	100.800	52.960
				19	84.000	51.906
				21	50.400	44.696
				23	23.400	32.248
				25	8.400	19.660
				27	3.360	12.424
				30	0.000	0.000
				low	32	1.680
			34		8.400	-12.176
			36		16.800	-11.510
			39		84.000	0.844
			42		215.040	19.482
			43	241.920	20.532	
44	268.800	20.380				

4.4.2. Surface sensors

General

The model is equipped with 6 modular surface sensors of type GRAS 48LX-1 (Figure 60). The 1mm thin microphone comes in dimension of 9mm x 18mm.

The ± 1 dB frequency range is 20Hz to 31.5kHz (product sheet, <https://www.grasacoustics.com/?eID=1709645390&product=336> and <https://www.grasacoustics.com/products/special-microphone/surface-microphones/product/828-gras-48lx-1-utp-microphone-medium-pressure>).

Mounting

The sensors (here #5) can be installed on the GRAS conical fairing (base diameter $\varnothing 29$ mm, cone angle 7.5°). Sensor #6 is mounted in the modified circular cover for under-wing flap brackets. The array of sensors #1-#4 is implemented in the modified cover insert for the over-wing flap bracket. The inserts were designed and 3D-printed by DLR.

Installation Position

The two sensors #5-6 are located on the main wing, while #1-4 are on the flap suction side. The X/Z-positions of the upstream sensors #1 and #3 approximately agree with flap pressure tap #21.

Figure 60: Position of surface microphones along the contour lines

Figure 61: Surface microphones on the model

Up to 8 channels were recorded during the test. The channel number including positions is listed in Table 17. The corresponding model axes and reference systems are described in section 4.2.1.

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Sensor 5 is listed with the fairing-mounted position as well as the projection onto the flap surface when ignoring the fairing dimensions.

Table 17: Channel list of acoustic instrumentation, as recorded by data acquisition system VIPER-24

Channel	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Sensor	Modular sensor array				Modular sensor	Modular sensor	Out of flow microphone
Type	GRAS 48LX-1 UTP				GRAS 48LX-1 UTP		GRAS 46AE
Element	flap				main wing		out of flow
Side	suction side				flap cove	pressure side	forward arc
Instrum. part	over-wing flap bracket pocket				none, use of GRAS fairing	Circular insert for flap bracket	first X95 rail
Orientation	<p>view from below</p>						
Axis Ref	FLE				WLE		AWB
X/C _{ref} [-]	15%	23%	15%	19%	88%	88%	55%
X [mm]	50.59	75.9	50.59	63.106	508.512	508.589 ^p	313.979
Y [mm]	-75.759	-75.759	-62.359	-62.359	-104.748	-104.748 ^p	-55.748
Z [mm]	44.495	50.535	44.495	48.038	53.102	54.339 ^p	-20.968
Axis Ref2	FTE (at $\delta_F=8^\circ$)				WTE		--
X [mm]	-279.115	-253.232	-279.115	-266.232	-67.586	-67.51 ^p	-262.119
Y [mm]	-75.759	-75.759	-62.359	-62.359	-104.748	-104.748 ^p	-55.748
Z [mm]	64.931	67.395	64.931	66.675	4.483	5.72 ^p	-69.587

p = alternative sensor position, sensor fairing is replaced by projection onto flap surface
 Channel 8 = time sync signal

The following settings were used for acquiring acoustic data points with VIPER-24:

- Test sample time: 30 seconds
- Test sample rate: 200 kHz
- Number of test samples: 6'000'000

4.4.3. Out of flow microphone

General

The out of flow microphone is a ½" free-field response microphone of type G.R.A.S. 46AE.

<https://www.grasacoustics.com/products/measurement-microphone-sets/constant-current-power-ccp-2/product/140-46ae#dimensions>

Installation

The sensor was mounted with a ½" clamp on a base plate (Figure 62). The base plate is taped to an X95 clamping carrier and mounted on the first set of X95-rails under the wing. The installation position is listed in Table 17.

Figure 62: Out of flow microphone

Acoustic Position

W.r.t. the seal trailing edge, the microphone positioned in the forward arc, at a polar angle of 66° (front-to-aft) and a distance of 1.059m. There is a slight azimuthal offset of 17° negative to the overhead plane (Y=0, i.e. the Laser plane). The microphone points directly (i.e. at zero incidence) towards the seal trailing edge, i.e. the measurement reference point.

Table 18: Out-of-flow microphone specifications

Point Channel		MRP	FF_01 7
	Manufacturer	[-]	GRAS
	Type	[-]	46AE
	Size	[-]	1/2"
	Calibration	[Pa/V]	19.0
	Incidence	[deg]	0.00
AWB - Installation coordinates	X	[m]	0.986
	Y	[m]	0.000
	Z	[m]	-0.015
Source coordinates	X	[m]	0
	Y	[m]	0
	Z	[m]	0
	Rcyl	[m]	0
	Rsph	[m]	0
	Phi (front-aft)	[deg]	0
	Psi (from overhead pos)	[deg]	0
			0.549
			-0.280
			-0.938
			-0.437
			-0.280
			-0.922
			0.964
			1.059
			66
			-17

Measurement range and corrections

The useful measurement range is 20Hz to 20kHz. The GRAS 46AE microphone correction curve in Figure 63 accounts for zero incidence and the grid effect. The curve is particularly smooth in the frequency range between 20Hz to ~11kHz.

Figure 63: Microphone Corrections

The trusted low frequency range depends on the noise generated by the rig (axial fan, heat exchanger, flow duct) as well as the properties of the anechoic test chamber which is defined by the acoustic treatment of the wall. A typical way to measure this background noise is to record datapoints with the Falcon model being removed. Unfortunately, the background noise test was not conducted. It can be checked whether pre-test background noise data can be made available.

4.4.4. Seal surveillance camera

One of the wind tunnel indoor surveillance cameras (named "Mobilkamera", type Bosch NBN-50051-C, 5 MegaPixel) was used for online observation of the state of seal excitement in order to avoid and potential destruction.

Figure 64: Seal surveillance with "Mobilkamera"

The camera is installed under the wing and observes the seal from an upstream position (Figure 63). All in all, 20 sequences were recorded (listed in Table 39). Note that the video files contain a false time stamp.

The most prominent video is sequence 1 which was presented during the test readiness review #2 on 13.06.2025 and the General Assembly GA3 on 01.07.2025.

Table 19: Records with seal surveillance camera “Mobilkamera”

Sequence [-]	Data point [-]	Date [DD.MM.YYYY]	Start [hh:mm:ss]	End [hh:mm:ss]	Duration Δt [mm:ss]	Duration Δt [sec]	Seal deflection	PIV Laser
1	72+	13.06.2025	12:11:02	12:14:03	03:01	180	X	
2	90+	13.06.2025	17:31:30	17:32:23	00:53	52	X	
3	91+	13.06.2025	17:45:19	17:46:04	00:45	44	X	
4	92+	16.06.2025	09:20:04	09:21:33	01:29	88	X	
5	106+	16.06.2025	11:06:07	11:07:29	01:22	81	X	
6	113+	16.06.2025	12:48:02	12:48:57	00:55	54	X	
7	118+	16.06.2025	15:39:13	15:43:49	04:36	275	X	
8	134+	16.06.2025	18:24:12	18:25:16	01:04	63		X
9	185+	23.06.2025	19:04:45	19:05:05	00:20	19		X
10	201+	23.06.2025	19:59:26	19:59:37	00:11	10		X
11	204+	23.06.2025	20:13:09	20:13:27	00:18	17		X
12	204+	23.06.2025	20:16:42	20:16:53	00:11	10		X
13	215+	24.06.2025	09:52:26	09:52:32	00:06	5		X
14	219+	24.06.2025	10:20:45	10:20:58	00:13	12		X
15	220+	24.06.2025	10:24:32	10:24:43	00:11	10		X
16	220+	24.06.2025	10:28:24	10:28:32	00:08	7		X
17	224+	24.06.2025	10:43:16	10:43:23	00:07	6		X
18	275+	26.06.2025	11:22:13	11:32:12	09:59	598	X	
19	275+	26.06.2025	11:33:03	11:33:26	00:23	22	X	
20	317+	26.06.2025	16:35:00	16:35:19	00:19	18		X

4.4.5. Time-synchronization

Channel 8 is a time-sync signal which allows to synchronize DLR-GO and DLR-BS data during the main test. The yellow background shade of a data point in Table 39 indicates that time-synchronization works. A green background shade indicates that the characteristic 5kHz tone and harmonics are not part of the spectrum and indicate that the window for synchronization has been missed.

4.4.6. High Speed Particle Image Velocimetry (PIV)

The particle image velocimetry (PIV) and image pattern correlation technique (IPCT, see section 4.4.7) tests were both designed and tested by DLR Göttingen. They are the defining part of the FALCON main test (section 5.3).

Due to the varying optical access into the flap cove, the rigging for the optical instrumentation differs between the two build configurations, i.e. F15LS wing with and without the flap (Figure 65).

Figure 65: Experimental setup of the PIV and IPCT of the configuration without flap (top) and with flap (bottom).

High-speed cameras

The PIV setup for the configuration **without flap** consists of two high-speed cameras (Phantom V2640) for 2D2C PIV measurements, i.e., the flow velocity in flow direction and in vertical direction are measured, in the wake of the airfoil. The first camera (PIV cam3) acquired particle images in the area above the seal, i.e. in the flap cove. The second camera (PIV cam4) acquired images of a larger field of view downstream of PIV cam3 and includes also the flow from the upper side of the airfoil and partially the wake of the airfoil.

The camera setup of the configuration **with flap** consists of three high-speed cameras (Phantom V2640), which are arranged for a 2D2C PIV measurement in the flap cove and a stereo or 2D3C PIV measurement on the upper side of the flap.

High-speed Laser

A high-speed laser (Photonics DM 150) was used to illuminate the particles during image acquisition. The laser including the power supply and cooler were positioned inside of the wind tunnel plenum at the downstream end, see Figure 66. The available laser power and light sheet optics resulted in a light sheet dimension of approximately 90 mm height and 2-3 mm thickness.

Figure 66 shows the laser light sheet and its orientation with respect to the model for the configuration without flap. The setup with flap required a more complex light sheet setup in order to partially illuminate also the flap cove with a laser light sheet from below. This was achieved by separating a part from the light sheet presented in Figure 67.

Figure 66: Laser light sheet (green) for particle illumination and LED illumination (yellow) for IPCT pattern illumination of the configuration without flap.

Data acquisition

PIV double images and IPCT images were acquired for approximately 3.9 s with 5 kHz and 2.5 kHz respectively. Thus, for every second PIV velocity vector field information on the shape of the seal is available. These measurements were conducted 10 times to acquire sufficient independent vector fields to achieve meaningful statistical results in the evaluation.

Preliminary results of the PIV and IPCT measurements for the configuration with flap are shown in Figure 67 and Figure 71, respectively.

Figure 67: PIV test planes and preliminary instantaneous PIV result for the configuration with flap.

4.4.7. 3D dynamic seal surface deformation measurements using IPCT

The IPCT measurement technique (image pattern correlation technique) utilizes a stereo camera system to acquire the displacement of markers on a surface to measure the deformation / movement of the surface.

The test setup (Figure 65) consists of a high-speed stereo-camera system (PCO.dimax) and two high-power LED arrays (HARDsoft) below the model for both build configurations. The IPCT system and PIV system were operated in a common to ensure a parallel recording of the 2 systems without interfering (see section 4.4.6).

The FALCON test surface is the seal side which is visible from the bottom of the wing. The **ICPT dot pattern** design by DLR-Go is described in section 4.3.1.

The data acquisitioning requires a wind-off reference test (see left images in Figure 68 and Figure 69) and a measurement recording (right side). The depicted seal is the L80 t0.1 steel seal with an example of the screen printed IPCT dot pattern.

In addition to the IPCT dot pattern (dot diameter of approximately 0.9 mm) **larger markers** were added to reference the fixed part of the seal and to provide an initial deformation for the evaluation. The marker positions detected in the images and their ID numbers are highlighted in green. The mutual field of view of both cameras is approximately 450 mm in spanwise direction.

Figure 68: IPCT CAM1 camera images of a seal made from stainless steel with the printed IPCT dot pattern. Wind-off reference image (left) and a wind-on measurement image (right) of DP298. Larger markers were glued for referencing the model fixed part of the seal and an initial flap deformation for the evaluation.

wind off

wind on (DP298, $U=34.3\text{m/s}$)

Figure 69: IPCT CAM2 camera images of a seal made from stainless steel with the printed IPCT dot pattern. Wind-off reference image (left) and a measurement image (right) of DP298. Larger markers were glued for referencing the model fixed part of the seal and an initial flap deformation for the evaluation.

Figure 70 and Figure 71 show preliminary results for DP298 with the sheet metal seal at 34.3 m/s. Camera movements are not corrected in the preliminary results. Where Figure 70 shows a time series of the z-coordinate of marker 7 placed close to the trailing edge of the seal, Figure 71 shows the deformation over the observed seal surface for the single frame #73. To determine the relative deformation of the seal the area placed between the mounting screws on the leading edge of the seal plane was fixed assuming this area is not affected by a deformation. The flow leads to a bending of the seal up to 18 mm at the trailing edge upwards reducing the gap to the flap remarkably compared to the wind-off state.

Figure 70: Preliminary IPCT result showing the vertical position of single marker of ID7 (see Figure 68) for datapoint DP 298.

Figure 71 preliminary IPCT result of a single frame#73 from DP298. Wind-off reference in grey.

4.4.8. Hot-wire Anemometry

General

Hotwire tests allow to measure velocity components simultaneously in turbulent, transient flow fields. The technology is based on a cooling effect between the flow and an electrically heated thin wire. A detailed description of the hot-wire measurement technique can be found in Bruun [1], Strickert [2] and Michel [3].

[1] H. Bruun, Hot-wire Anemometry - Principals and signal analysis, Oxford University Press, 1995.

[2] H. Strickert, Hitzdraht- und Hitzfilmanemometrie, VEB Verlag, 1974.

[3] U. Michel und E. Froebel, "Lower limit for the velocity fluctuation level in wind tunnels," Experiments in fluids 6.1, pp. 49-54, 1988

The most widely used hot-wire measurement technique is constant temperature anemometry (CTA): The electrical resistance of the sensor wire and thus its temperature is kept constant via a feedback amplifier. The wire is part of a Wheatstone bridge.

Tested model builds

The hot wire tests were conducted for the Falcon baseline configuration from the main test: The F15LSmod is inclined to $\alpha_{geo}=1^\circ$. It contains the adapted flap cove geometry, albeit without any seal.

Instrumentation

The initial test idea was to use DLR's right-angled dual wire probes in X-array arrangement in order to measure two-dimensional flow properties. Unfortunately, the sensitive wires were destroyed in the early stage of test.

Hence, the workaround was to acquire all data points with single wire probes: the 55P14 is a miniature wire probe (diameter: $\varnothing 5 \mu\text{m}$, length: 1.25 mm, material: platinum-plated tungsten) which has right-angled prongs and a sensor which is aligned perpendicular to the probe axis (Figure 72).

More information is provided by the manufacturer at:

<https://www.dantecdynamics.com/product/minature-wire-probe-right-angle-perpendicular/><https://www.dantecdynamics.com/product/minature-wire-probe-right-angle-perpendicular/>

55P14

image: <https://www.dantecdynamics.com/wp-content/uploads/2017/06/products-55p14.png>

90° sensor perpendicular to probe axis

Figure 72: Hot-wire probe 55 P14, left: geometry ©Dantec Dynamics, right: test probe #45 at AWB

Instrumentation Hardware

A 55P14 single wire probe was installed on a straight mounting tube and fixed on DLR's ISEL® three-axes traversing unit. The traversing unit is located on the door side (Y-) of the wind tunnel (see Figure 73). Each traversing axis is co-aligned with the wind tunnel axis, i.e. no axis moves in reverse AWB direction.

Figure 73: Hot-wire test setup

The Y-traversing position is fixed to $Y=0$, the same plane which has been used for the PIV measurements.

The traversing reference point is $X=884.073\text{mm}$ and $Z=-171.218\text{mm}$ (in AWB coordinates). This value has been found by locating a geometric reference (i.e. the seal interface position) at $X_{\text{HW}}=22\text{mm}$ and $Z_{\text{HW}}=153\text{mm}$ (in traversing coordinates).

Traversing is implemented in machine units; hence online data values must be converted into millimeters via division by 80 to account for the pitch of the trapezoidal thread.

Data acquisition

DLR uses the TSI IFA300 by ©TSI Incorporated with the ThermalPro Data Acquisition and Analysis software. The data is initially locally stored on a separate computer in folders with the name convention "plane + WT speed", e.g. "COVE34".

This means that the system runs independently from otherwise centrally controlled AWB software. The listed data points 367-380 in the test run down sheet (Table 39) serve only as time stamps to post-process auxiliary data such as test rig operational data from backup logs, if this is of any interest.

Figure 74: Hot-wire measurement planes

Measurement Planes

The measurement planes are listed in :

- Flap cove 1 (COVE) is a plane of $\Delta X=66\text{mm} \times \Delta Z=72\text{mm}$ which is resolved in steps of $\Delta=2\text{mm}$. The presence of the main wing is addressed in the grid by omitting parts of the top left corner. The 1185 points are traversed in alternating vertical direction, starting from bottom left and moving slowly in X-direction. The plane contains some irregularities which make triangulation necessary: the missing top left corner, three missing positions in the remaining grid and one repeated position.
- Flap cove 2 (COVE2) is the extension of Flap cove 1 and was measured as a bonus at the end of the campaign. It is a plane of $\Delta X=66\text{mm} \times \Delta Z=30\text{mm}$ which is resolved in steps of $\Delta=2\text{mm}$. The upper X-row is a repetition of the lowest row in flap cove 1. The 544 points are traversed in alternating vertical direction, starting from bottom left and moving slowly in X-direction. *The usability of this bonus data depends on a successful calibration, since a second single wire probe was used on the initial calibration of the then-broken first single wire probe.*
- FlapTE (FLPTE) is a vertical line which is located in the wake of the model at $X_{\text{HW}}=456\text{mm}$, i.e. just downstream the flap trailing edge. It features 77 points which are traversed in top-down direction along a length of $\Delta Z=226\text{mm}$. The resolution is $\Delta=4\text{mm}$ for the first 38 points, changing to $\Delta=2\text{mm}$ in the vicinity and below the flap trailing edge.

Table 20: Hot-wire test plane properties

Plane	Cove	Cove2	FlapTE
X_{HW} [mm]	20:2:86	20:2:86	456
Z_{HW} [mm]	-12:2:60	-42:2:-12	115:-4:-33 & -35:-2:-111
Res. Δ [mm]	2	2	2-4
ΔX [mm]	66	66	-
ΔZ [mm]	72	30	226
#points [-]	1185	544	77
Traversing	vertical	vertical	vertical
	alternating	alternating	--
start	bottom left	bottom left	top

For safe traversing without any collision, each traversing path contains 4 additional points at the start which move each axis individually from the traversing reference point to the start point of the plane.

There are also 4 points at the end, which traverse the hot-wire from the last measurement point back to the traversing reference point.

Test conduction

The test was conducted for the two wind tunnel speeds of 34.3 m/s and 60 m/s. The test order is listed in Table 21.

Table 21: Hot-wire test plan

Test date	Plane	WT Speed U [m/s]	Single Wire Probe
07.07.2025 15:27	COVE	34.3	#46
07.07.2025 18:26	COVE	60	#46
07.07.2025 21:03	FLPTE	60	#46
07.07.2025 21:16	FLPTE	34.3	#46
08.07.2025 08:50	COVE2	34.3	#44

5. Test Matrix and Test Conduction

5.1. Overview

A test readiness review meeting has been conducted on Fr, 05.06.2025. The FALCON test ended 23 work days later on Tu, 08.07.2025. Data points were acquired on 10 days while 13 full days were needed for in-test rigging as well as instrumentation setups.

The full parameter set of the FALCON test matrix consists of 10 parameters. Even the best tries of reducing the test by merging parameters (towards 7) leads to a cardinality of almost 200k data points (Table 22), i.e. far too many to be tested.

Table 22: Estimation of maximal data point number for the full FALCON test parameter set

FALCON – FULL PARAMETER SET									
1x ops	2x wing build		3x flap build				1x seal		
WT speed [m/s]	α_{geo} [deg]	BL fence installed [-]	flap installed [-]	Flap δ_F [deg]	Gap [mm]	OvL [mm]	seal material [-]	length [mm]	thick-ness [mm]
U0	a-3°	yes	yes	8°	15.2	102.8	<i>no seal</i>	--	--
...	a-2°	<i>noBLf.</i>	<i>noflap</i>	14°	14.456	80.538	Blank St.	L50	t0.15
U28	a-1°				15.2	94.405	PIV Steel	L80	t0.1
U32	a+0°				15.2	98.199	Airbus		t0.2
U34.3	a+1°				29.2	90.995	TPU		t0.5
...	a+2°				22.2	94.132			t3...6
U60	a+3°				29.55	90.995			t6
33	8	2	2	2	7		13		
>192k									

Hence, the test had to be split into sub-campaigns with 2 or max. 3 meta parameters which are easy to change with in the sub-campaign. The cost of each test parameter was estimated in terms of build change time. The most cost-effective parameter is the wind tunnel speed. The other cost functions also depend on the used instrumentation, i.e. test with or without PIV equipment, and are not listed here.

The efforts reduced the test to 7 sub-campaigns and a maximal data point number of 573 (Table 23). The matrix was further thinned out ("sparse matrix") to an actually measured data point number of 380.

Table 23: Estimation of maximal data point number using sub-campaigns

Full parameter set	33	8	2	2	2	7	13		192192
sub-campaign	WT speed	Incidence α_{geo}	BL fence installed	flap installed	Flap dF	Gap/OvL	seal	instrum.	Cardinality
Wing Aero – Seal selection	17	2					4		136
Wing Aero – Alpha selection	3	7							21
Wing Aero – Gap/OvL	25					6			150
Main Test – no flap	8		2	no			4		64
Main Test – flap installed	16						6		96
Main Test – PIV repetitions								100	100
Hot Wire Test								6	6
Combined sub-campaigns									Σ573

The build list table is attached below (Table 24) where build changes are indicated in blue. The full test run down sheet is attached as Table 37.

Table 24: Build list

Build ID	start dpt [-]	BL Fence [-]	Wing AoA [°]	Flap inst. [-]	flap setting [-]	gap [mm]	overlap OvL [mm]	tripping ID [-]	seal mat. [-]	seal length L [mm]	seal thickn. t [mm]	Comment
#1	1	#1	0°	X	#1	15.2	108.2	--	holder	--	--	
#2	14	#1	0°	X	#1	15.2	108.2	--	blank St.	80	0.2	
	18	#1	0°	X	#1	15.2	108.2	--	blank St.	80	0.2	out-of-flow mic inst.
#3	22	#1	0°	X	#1	15.2	108.2	--	blank St.	50	0.15	
	26	#1	-3°	X	#1	15.2	108.2	--	blank St.	50	0.15	
	29	#1	-2°	X	#1	15.2	108.2	--	blank St.	50	0.15	
	32	#1	-1°	X	#1	15.2	108.2	--	blank St.	50	0.15	
	35	#1	1°	X	#1	15.2	108.2	--	blank St.	50	0.15	
	38	#1	2°	X	#1	15.2	108.2	--	blank St.	50	0.15	
	41	#1	3°	X	#1	15.2	108.2	--	blank St.	50	0.15	
	44	#1	1°	X	#1	15.2	108.2	--	blank St.	50	0.15	
#4	52	#1	1°	X	#1	15.2	108.2	--	holder	--	--	
#5	57	#1	1°	X	#1	15.2	108.2	--	blank St.	20	0.2	
#6	65	#1	1°	X	#1	15.2	108.2	--	blank St.	80	0.1	
#7	74	#1b	1°	X	#2	14.456	80.584	--	blank St.	80	0.1	
#8	93	#1c	1°	X	#3	15.2	95.451	--	blank St.	80	0.1	
#9	107	#1d	1°	X	#4	15.2	98.246	--	blank St.	80	0.1	
#10	114	#1e	1°	X	#5	29.2	90.741	--	blank St.	80	0.1	
#11	119	#1e	1°	X	#5	29.2	90.741	#1	blank St.	80	0.1	
#12	124	#1f	1°	X	#6	22.2	94.185	#1	blank St.	80	0.1	
#13	135	#2	1°	no	--	--	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.5	
#14	158	#2	1°	no	--	--	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.2	
#15	168	#2	1°	no	--	--	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.1	
#16	186	#2	1°	no	--	--	--	--	holder	--	--	
#17	205	#2	1°	no	--	--	--	--	holder	--	--	no BL fence
#18	227	#3	1°	X	#7	29.55	90.741	#2	Airbus	50	3	
#19	251	#3	1°	X	#7	29.55	90.741	#2	TPU V2	50	6	
#20	259	#3	1°	X	#7	29.55	90.741	#2	PIV Steel	50	0.1	
#21	267	#3	1°	X	#7	29.55	90.741	#2	PIV Steel	80	0.12	
#22	300	#3	1°	X	#7	29.55	90.741	#2	PIV Steel	80	0.22	
#23	320	#3	1°	X	#7	29.55	90.741	#2	holder	--	--	
#24	356	#3	1°	X	#7	29.55	90.741	#2	holder	--	--	PIV rigging removed
#25	367	#3	1°	X	#7	29.55	90.741	#2	holder	--	--	hot-wire rigging inst.

5.2. Wing Aerodynamics sub-campaign

The sub-campaign had the objective to fix the wing incidence and the flap position for the main test, to find suitable seals for the main test and find the critical wind tunnel speeds which correspond to the excitation of the seal. A further objective is to find the geometrical to physical alpha conversion for comparable wing aerodynamics in order to be able to cross-compare open test section experiment and numerical simulation.

The wing aerodynamics sub-campaign started with the reference flap position (flap setting #1):

- Flap deflection angle $\delta_F=8^\circ$
- Gap = 15.2mm
- Overlap OvL = 108.2mm

The wing aerodynamics sub-campaign was further split into down-selection tests for:

- the seal (section 5.2.1)
- the wing-incidence (section 5.2.25.2.3)
- the flap setting (section 5.2.3)

All in all, it was conducted three work days after the pre-poned test readiness review. Data points were measured during three work days. The testing was interrupted by a second meeting on Fr., 03.06.2025.

Table 25: test plan of wing aerodynamics sub-campaign

WING AERODYNAMICS							
		Mo, 09.06.2025	Tu, 10.06.2025	We, 11.06.2025	Th, 12.06.2025	Fr, 13.06.2025	Mo, 16.06.2025
9:00	10:00	bank holiday	Rigging	Initial Setup Instrumentation checks	PIV rigging	blank seal L20 t0.2	Gap/OvL L80 t0.1 AR1.0 Gap 15.2 AR0.75 Gap 15.2 AR0.75 Gap 29.2 AR0.75 Gap 22.2
10:00	11:00						
11:00	12:00						
12:00	13:00						
13:00	14:00				Seal test L80 t0.2		
14:00	15:00				Alpha test L50 t0.15	TRR2	
15:00	16:00				No seal	Gap/OvL L80 t0.1 AR0.45 Gap 15.2 AR2.0 Gap 15.2	
16:00	17:00						
17:00	18:00						
18:00	19:00						
19:00	20:00						

5.2.1. Seal down-selection

The objective of the seal down-selection was to identify a suitable seal for the main test with PIV. Four blank steel seals were tested (Table 26) with the flap at setting #1.

The excited seals are L80 t0.1 and also L80 t0.2. The necessary seal aspect ratio is in the range $L/t > 400$ (Table 27).

Table 26: Seal selection test: reduced test parameter set

WING AERODYNAMICS – SEAL DOWN-SELECTION									
1x ops	2x wing build		3x flap build				1x seal		
WT speed [m/s]	α_{geo} [deg]	BL fence installed [-]	flap installed [-]	Flap δ_F [deg]	Gap [mm]	OvL [mm]	seal material [-]	length [mm]	thick-ness [mm]
U0 U20 ... U60 U63.3	$a+0^\circ$ $a+1^\circ$	yes	yes	8°	15.2	102.8	Blank St.	L80 t0.2 L50 t0.15 L20 t0.2 L80 t0.1	
17	2	1	1	1	1		1	4	=136

Table 27: Seal test data points (12.-13.06.): structured test matrix

Seal	Blank St.	Blank St.	Blank St.	Blank St.	Blank St.	no seal
Length L [mm]	L80	L50	L50	L20	L80	
thickness t [mm]	t0.2	t0.15	t0.15	t0.2	t0.1	
L/t [-]	400	333	333	100	800	
α_{geo} [deg]	0°	0°	1°	1°	1°	1°
30 m/s	18	23	44	58	70	52
35 m/s			45	59		
40 m/s	19		46	60		53
45 m/s		24	47	61		54
50 m/s	20		48	62		55
55 m/s			49	63		
60 m/s	21	25	50	64		56
63.3 m/s			51			
Max. WT Speed	60 m/s	60 m/s	63.3 m/s	60 m/s	34 m/s	
Π^{-1} =Aero/Bend	18	11	12	0.28	47	

5.2.2. Wing incidence down-selection

The wing incidence down-selection was conducted with the blank steel seal L50 t0.15 at setting #1 (Table 28). The reduced test parameters set of geometric incidences vs. wind tunnel speed is listed in the structured test matrix (Table 29).

The test showed no clear preference for any particular wing incidence α_{geo} . Based on spectra at surface microphone MOD#5 (Figure 75), $\alpha_{geo}=1^\circ$ was chosen for the remaining test.

Table 28: Wing incidence test: reduced test parameter set

WING AERODYNAMICS - INCIDENCE / ALPHA DOWN-SELECTION									
1x ops	2x wing build		3x flap build				1x seal		
WT speed [m/s]	α_{geo} [deg]	BL fence installed [-]	flap installed [-]	Flap δ_F [deg]	Gap [mm]	OvL [mm]	seal material [-]	length [mm]	thick-ness [mm]
U30 U45 U60	a-3° a-2° a-1° a+0° a+1° a+2° a+3°	yes	yes	8°	15.2	102.8	Blank St.	L50 t0.15	
3	7	1	1	1	1		1	1	= 21

Table 29: Wing incidence data points (12.06.): structured test matrix

α_{geo} [deg]	-3°	-2°	-1°	0°	1°	2°	3°
30 m/s	26	29	32	23	35	38	41
45 m/s	27	30	33	24	36	39	42
60 m/s	28	31	34	25	37	40	43

Figure 75: Wing incidence, online cross-comparison.

5.2.3. Flap setting down-selection

The objective of the test is to find a suitable flap position for the main test. The test was conducted with a constant flap deflection angle of 8° and the L80°t0.1 seal (Table 30).

The internal flow properties of the flap cove flow contours were analyzed in order to develop a suitable test hypothesis. The analysis is conducted with the geometry assumption of a rigid seal or zero flow.

Figure 76: FALCON flap settings

The **flap cove inlet** is characterized by the distance between seal trailing edge and the flap leading edge Figure 76. Hence, it depends on seal length and overlap.

The **flap cove outlet** is characterized by the closest distance between main wing and flap, i.e. the gap parameter (assuming converging duct geometry).

An internal flow analysis determines discharge coefficients based on pressure losses (wall friction and flow turning) as well as smallest flow area (throat).

The smallest flow area depends on the flap cove inlet to outlet area ratio AR (Table 8):

$$\text{Flap cove Area ratio} \quad AR := \frac{\text{Inlet}}{\text{Outlet}} = \frac{\Delta(\text{Seal-FlapLE}) \cdot b}{\text{Gap} \cdot b} = \frac{\Delta(\text{Seal-FlapLE})}{\text{Gap}} \quad (1)$$

Conventional flap cove flow is characterized by a converging duct geometry: The area ratio is greater than unity (AR>1, or Outlet area < Inlet area). The seal is not particularly important in the consideration of pressure losses and flow discharge.

This changes in the other case (AR<1, or inlet area < outlet), were a rigid seal restricts the flap cove flow hydraulics by a small inlet area and higher flow turning losses.

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Both of the two cases (inlet-driven flow hydraulics vs. outlet-driven flow hydraulics) were tested. The goal is to find a setting (1) with seal excitation at a characteristic wind tunnel velocity while (2) increasing the observable flow field of the PIV test. The full length of the elongated holes of the Gap-brackets and OvL-brackets was used. Following the idea of the Design of Experiments method¹, radical settings were prioritized in the test order.

The Gap-values in sub-test 1 with flap settings 1-4 are kept constant while the inlet area is changed. An interesting observation is that flap settings with AR>1 allow to test much larger wind tunnel speeds (Table 31) before reaching visible seal excitation.

At AR=2, the characteristic seal excitation in streamwise direction was not observed. While the seal moves rather erratic, the main action happens at both of the sidewise clamping position where the seal tapes were finally damaged. At AR=1, the seal excitation occurs at slightly higher wind tunnel speed. Lower area ratios, e.g. AR0.75, reproduce the characteristic seal excitation of the reference well and deliver clean frequency spectra.

Therefore, the area ratio of 0.75 remained constant in sub-test 2 (flap settings 4-6). Both, inlet area and outlet area were further increased in the limits of the flap brackets in order to potentially gain greater visibility in the flap cove.

The better optical access was also the reason why flap setting #5 was chosen for the main test. The PIV BL fence (initially for the main wing element only) was adapted with standard tools mid-test to feature flap setting #5. The realized Gap after installation was measured with Johansson gauge blocks and was labelled as a new flap setting, i.e. #7.

Table 30: Gap/Overlap test: reduced test parameter set

WING AERODYNAMICS - GAP/OVL DOWN-SELECTION									
1x ops	2x wing build		3x flap build				1x seal		
WT speed [m/s]	α_{geo} [deg]	BL fence installed [-]	flap installed [-]	Flap δ_F [deg]	Gap [mm]	OvL [mm]	seal material [-]	length [mm]	thick-ness [mm]
U0 ... U28 U32 U34.3 ... U60	a+1°	yes	yes	8°	15.2 14.456 15.2 15.2 29.2 22.2	102.8 80.538 94.405 98.199 90.995 94.132	Blank St.	L80 t0.1	
25	1	1	1	1	6		1	1	=150

¹ This method relies on multi-parameter design space exploration of the extreme combinations of factors (parameters) that contributes to a specific set of responses. Once the optimum set-up is encountered, the “hard factors”, e.g. the flap setting, can be fixed.

Table 31: Gap/Overlap data points (13.+16.06.): structured test matrix

Flap Setting	1	2	3	4	5	5	6	6 (rpt)
AR	0.45	2	1	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.75
Gap	15.2	14.5	15.2	15.2	29.2	29.2	22.2	22.2
Tripping	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1
28 m/s	69	78	97	107	114	119	124	
30 m/s	70	79	98	108	115	120	125	133
32 m/s	71	80	100	109	117	122	126	134
34 m/s	73	81	102	110	118	123	127	
36 m/s		82	104	111			128	
38 m/s		83	106	112			129	
40 m/s		84					130	
42 m/s		85						
44 m/s		86						
46 m/s		87						
48 m/s		88						
50 m/s		89						
51 m/s		90						
55 m/s		91						
data point	73	92	106	113	118	123	131	134
Crit. WT Speed	34 m/s	50 m/s	38 m/s	39 m/s	33.5 m/s	33.5 m/s	41 m/s	32 m/s
Π^{-1} =Aero/Bend	47	101	58	61	45	45	68	41

5.3. Main test / PIV sub-campaign

The main test was conducted with the test team from DLR-Go during the 9 test days between 17.06.-27.06.2024. The sub-campaign can be further separated in the tests without (section 5.3.1) and with the flap being installed (section 5.3.2):

- The tests of the main wing without any flap provide good optical access into the flap cove. This is why it was defined as the PIV backup case.
- The tests with the flap being installed provide less optical access into the flap cove, but are much closer to the actual research problem.

The PIV test system is limited by the camera's local data storage allowing to record a few test seconds. For statistic representability, each data point needed to be repeated 10 times. The download time for each repetition is approximately 5 minutes. Testing one data point takes up with 10 repetitions takes 45mins to 1h and generates a data set of a substantial data size. Hence, 5 to 10 data points can be measured altogether. In Falcon, 10 statistically viable datapoints have been tested.

These conditions affect the way how the test is conducted: After installing a particular test build, the acoustic test equipment was used to scout out a valuable data point in order to conduct the PIV tests.

Table 32: test plan of PIV sub-campaign

		PIV TEST CAMPAIGN						
		Tu, 17. - Fr, 20.06.2025	Mo, 23.06.2025	Tu, 24.06.2025	We, 25.06.2025	Th, 26.06.2025	Fr, 27.06.2025	
9:00	10:00	PIV Rigging & Calibration 20.06.2025 3 Test points w/wind	PIV Calibration	No BLfence (10)	PIV Calibration	seal L50 t0.1	No seal	
10:00	11:00			Flap insert machined in main BLfence re-install flap PIV rigging for new build		Airbus sealing L50 t3 (10)	Calibrate for L80	PIV De-Rigging
11:00	12:00						seal L80 t0.1 (20) seal L80 t0.2 (10)	
12:00	13:00							
13:00	14:00						TPU sealing L50 t6	
14:00	15:00							
15:00	16:00						No seal (10)	
16:00	17:00							
17:00	18:00						No seal (10)	
18:00	19:00							
19:00	20:00	No seal (10)						

values in brackets represent number of PIV-data points

5.3.1. Wing w/o flap

The tests of the main wing without any flap are the PIV backup case. They are closely related to the AWB Pre-Test's "CONF-D" build (measured in Dec-2024).

The data points were generated for the three L=80mm PIV Steel seals, the build configuration without any seal as well as without any boundary layer fence (Table 33). PIV data points were acquired for wind tunnel speeds of 60 m/s, acoustic datapoints are listed in Table 34. Some acoustic data points contain 5kHz tones and harmonics (10kHz, 15kHz, ...), since the PIV equipment was tested out.

Table 33: Main test 1 "Wing w/o flap" (23.-24.06.), reduced test parameter set

MAIN TEST Phase 1: Wing without flap									
1x ops	2x wing build		3x flap build				2x seal		
WT speed	α_{geo}	BL fence installed	flap installed	Flap δ_F	Gap	OvL	seal material	length	thick-ness
[m/s]	[deg]	[-]	[-]	[deg]	[mm]	[mm]	[-]	[mm]	[mm]
U0	a+1°	yes	<i>noflap</i>	--	--	--	no seal	--	--
U30		noBLf.					PIV Steel	L80 t0.5	
U35							PIV Steel	L80 t0.2	
...							PIV Steel	L80 t0.1	
U60									
8	1	2	1	1	1	1	4	= 64	

Table 34: Main test 1 "Wing w/o flap" (23.-24.06.), structured test matrix w/ acoustic datapoints

name	L80 t0.5	L80 t0.2	L80 t0.1	no seal	no BLfence
Length L [mm]	80	80	80	--	--
thickness t [mm]	0.5	0.2	0.1	--	--
BL fence	X	X	X	X	--
0 m/s	157	158	185	186	205
30 m/s	140	159	171	187*	206
35 m/s	142*	160*	172*	188	207*
40 m/s	143	161	173	189*	208
45 m/s	144	162	174*	190	209
50 m/s	145	163	168	191	210
55 m/s	146	164	169	192	211
60 m/s	147*	165*	170	187	212

* data point contains 5kHz tone + harmonics from Laser

5.3.2. Wing w/flap

The tests with the re-installed flap required considerable rigging efforts. This does not only concern the ad-hoc manufacturing of the boundary layer fence, reinstallation of the flap and flap instrumentation checks: The PIV equipment had to be adjusted for the new build configuration (see Figure 65).

The test features three L=50mm seals of varying material and thickness as well as two L=80mm PIV Steel seals.

The configuration without seal (no seal, Table 36) was last PIV build. This build was also repeated after de-rigging of the PIV equipment (no seal #2) which allows to judge the influence of the PIV hardware onto the acoustic test.

Table 35: Main test 2 "Wing w/ flap" (25.-27.06.), reduced test parameter set

MAIN TEST Phase 2: Wing with flap									
1x ops	2x wing build		3x flap build				1x seal		
WT speed [m/s]	α_{geo} [deg]	BL fence installed [-]	flap installed [-]	Flap δ_F [deg]	Gap [mm]	OvL [mm]	seal material [-]	length [mm]	thick-ness [mm]
U0 U32 U34.3 ... U60	a+1°	yes	yes	8°	29.55	90.995	Airbus TPU PIV Steel PIV Steel PIV Steel no seal	L50 t3..6 L50 t6 L50 t0.1 L80 t0.1 L80 t0.2 --	
16	1	1	1	1	1				= 96

Table 36: Main test 2 "Wing w/ flap" (25.-27.06.), structured test matrix w/ acoustic datapoints

name	Airbus	TPU	PIV Steel	PIV Steel	PIV Steel	No Seal	No Seal #2
Length L [mm]	50	50	50	80	80	--	--
thickness t [mm]	3	6	0.1	0.1	0.2	--	--
0 m/s	230	251	259	267	300	340	356
30 m/s	232	252	260	270	301	343	357
35 m/s	233	253	261		302	349	360
40 m/s	234	254	262		303	350	361
45 m/s	235	255	263		304	351	362
50 m/s	236	256	264		305	352	363
55 m/s	237	257	265		306	353	364
60 m/s	238	258	266		307	354	365

5.4. Hot-wire sub-campaign

After the de-rigging the PIV setup, the foam boxes were rearranged for proper installation of the hot-wire setup. The procedure of traversing hardware installation and alignment, setup of measurement system and troubleshooting took ~5 days.

The test was conducted on July 07-08 and its order listed in Table 21.

Table 37: test plan of hot-wire test sub-campaign

		HOT-WIRE					
		Mo, 30.06.2025	Tu, 01.07.2025	We, 02. - Fr, 04.07.2025	Mo, 07.07.2025	Tu, 08.07.2025	
9:00	10:00	Hotwire Rigging	FALCONGA3 online	Hardware test	Hardware test	Cove2	
10:00	11:00					De-Rigging End of Test	
11:00	12:00						
12:00	13:00						
13:00	14:00						
14:00	15:00						
15:00	16:00						Cove
16:00	17:00						
17:00	18:00						
18:00	19:00						
19:00	20:00				FlapTE		

Table 38: test plan of hot-wire test sub-campaign

HOT-WIRE Test								
1x ops	2x wing build		3x flap build				seal	HOT-WIRE
WT speed [m/s]	α_{geo} [deg]	BL fence installed [-]	flap installed [-]	Flap δ_F [deg]	Gap [mm]	OvL [mm]	seal material [-]	plane position [-]
U34.3 U60	a+1°	yes	yes	8°	29.55	90.995	no seal	COVE FLPTE (COVE2)
2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	3
								= 6

Table 39: Test run down sheet, as recorded by DLR-BS

Date [MM.DD. JJ]	Data Point [-]	PIV dpt [-]	Speed U [m/sec]	Wing AoA [°]	gap [mm]	overlap OvL [mm]	seal mat. [-]	seal length L [mm]	seal thickn. t [mm]	aspect ratio L/t [-]	Bend/ Aero 1/PI [-]	Comment
INSTRUMENTATION TESTS												
PSI-Test												
flap installed at initial $\delta F=8^\circ$ reference position: Gap-Bracket=17.000, OvL-Bracket=34.738, Gap=15.200, OvL=102.800												
[1] DLR-F15LSmod, ref flap, no seal												
11.06.25	1		28	0	15.2	108.2	holder	--	--	0	0	
11.06.25	2		28	0	15.2	108.2	holder	--	--	0	0	
11.06.25	3		28	0	15.2	108.2	holder	--	--	0	0	
11.06.25	4		40	0	15.2	108.2	holder	--	--	0	0	BLf nose flutter
11.06.25	5		30	0	15.2	108.2	holder	--	--	0	0	
11.06.25	6		30	0	15.2	108.2	holder	--	--	0	0	
11.06.25	7		30	0	15.2	108.2	holder	--	--	0	0	
11.06.25	8		30	1.1	15.2	108.2	holder	--	--	0	0	
Nose of boundary layer fence shortened from elliptical to ~circular to reduce fluttering												
Wind Tunnel PIV protection: Alu plate 500x180x3 installed at Z+ position of AWB nozzle												
12.06.25	9		30	0	15.2	108.2	holder	--	--	0	0	
12.06.25	10		40	0	15.2	108.2	holder	--	--	0	0	
12.06.25	11		50	0	15.2	108.2	holder	--	--	0	0	
12.06.25	12		60	0	15.2	108.2	holder	--	--	0	0	
12.06.25	13		30	0	15.2	108.2	holder	--	--	0	0	
adapted BL fence nose is good for testing												
Collector dZ=100mm to Z=610mm (floor-to-collector distance)												
[2] DLR-F15LSmod, ref flap, blank seal L80 t0.2												
12.06.25	14		30	0	15.2	108.2	blank St.	80	0.2	400	4.5	
12.06.25	15		40	0	15.2	108.2	blank St.	80	0.2	400	8.1	
12.06.25	16		50	0	15.2	108.2	blank St.	80	0.2	400	13	
12.06.25	17		60	0	15.2	108.2	blank St.	80	0.2	400	18	
½" Mic installed, new microphone setup												
SEAL TESTS PRIOR TO MAIN TEST												
[2] DLR-F15LSmod, ref flap, blank seal L80 t0.2												
12.06.25	18		30	0	15.2	108.2	blank St.	80	0.2	400	4.5	
12.06.25	19		40	0	15.2	108.2	blank St.	80	0.2	400	8.1	
12.06.25	20		50	0	15.2	108.2	blank St.	80	0.2	400	13	
12.06.25	21		60	0	15.2	108.2	blank St.	80	0.2	400	18	
DLR-GO rigging, seal changed												
ALPHA TEST												
[3] DLR-F15LSmod, ref flap, blank seal L50 t0.15												
12.06.25	22		0	0	15.2	108.2	blank St.	50	0.15	333	0	no controls
12.06.25	23		30	0	15.2	108.2	blank St.	50	0.15	333	2.6	
12.06.25	24		45	0	15.2	108.2	blank St.	50	0.15	333	5.9	
12.06.25	25		60	0	15.2	108.2	blank St.	50	0.15	333	11	
change alpha												

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Date [MM.DD. JJ]	Data Point [-]	PIV dpt [-]	Speed U [m/sec]	Wing AoA [°]	gap [mm]	overlap OvL [mm]	seal mat. [-]	seal length L [mm]	seal thickn. t [mm]	aspect ratio L/t [-]	Bend/ Aero 1/PI [-]	Comment
12.06.25	26		30	-3	15.2	108.2	blank St.	50	0.15	333	2.6	
12.06.25	27		45	-3	15.2	108.2	blank St.	50	0.15	333	5.9	
12.06.25	28		60	-3	15.2	108.2	blank St.	50	0.15	333	11	
change alpha												
12.06.25	29		30	-2	15.2	108.2	blank St.	50	0.15	333	2.6	
12.06.25	30		45	-2	15.2	108.2	blank St.	50	0.15	333	5.9	
12.06.25	31		60	-2	15.2	108.2	blank St.	50	0.15	333	11	
change alpha												
12.06.25	32		30	-1	15.2	108.2	blank St.	50	0.15	333	2.6	
12.06.25	33		45	-1	15.2	108.2	blank St.	50	0.15	333	5.9	
12.06.25	34		60	-1	15.2	108.2	blank St.	50	0.15	333	11	
change alpha												
12.06.25	35		30	1	15.2	108.2	blank St.	50	0.15	333	2.6	false comment
12.06.25	36		45	1	15.2	108.2	blank St.	50	0.15	333	5.9	
12.06.25	37		60	1	15.2	108.2	blank St.	50	0.15	333	11	
change alpha												
12.06.25	38		30	2	15.2	108.2	blank St.	50	0.15	333	2.6	
12.06.25	39		45	2	15.2	108.2	blank St.	50	0.15	333	5.9	
12.06.25	40		60	2	15.2	108.2	blank St.	50	0.15	333	11	false comment
change alpha												
12.06.25	41		30	3	15.2	108.2	blank St.	50	0.15	333	2.6	
12.06.25	42		45	3	15.2	108.2	blank St.	50	0.15	333	5.9	
12.06.25	43		60	3	15.2	108.2	blank St.	50	0.15	333	11	
change alpha to +1deg (produces max peak)												
12.06.25	44		30	1	15.2	108.2	blank St.	50	0.15	333	2.6	
12.06.25	45		35	1	15.2	108.2	blank St.	50	0.15	333	3.6	
12.06.25	46		40	1	15.2	108.2	blank St.	50	0.15	333	4.7	
12.06.25	47		45	1	15.2	108.2	blank St.	50	0.15	333	5.9	
12.06.25	48		50	1	15.2	108.2	blank St.	50	0.15	333	7.3	
12.06.25	49		55	1	15.2	108.2	blank St.	50	0.15	333	8.8	
12.06.25	50		60	1	15.2	108.2	blank St.	50	0.15	333	11	
12.06.25	51		63.3	1	15.2	108.2	blank St.	50	0.15	333	12	
remove seal, 15x15mm seal adapter remains installed												
[4] DLR-F15LSmod, ref flap, no seal, holder												
12.06.25	52		30	1	15.2	108.2	holder	--	--	0	0	
12.06.25	53		40	1	15.2	108.2	holder	--	--	0	0	
12.06.25	54		45	1	15.2	108.2	holder	--	--	0	0	
12.06.25	55		50	1	15.2	108.2	holder	--	--	0	0	
12.06.25	56		60	1	15.2	108.2	holder	--	--	0	0	
decision: keep alpha_geo = 1deg												
change seal												
dPAMB installed												

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Date [MM.DD. JJ]	Data Point [-]	PIV dpt [-]	Speed U [m/sec]	Wing AoA [°]	gap [mm]	overlap OvL [mm]	seal mat. [-]	seal length L [mm]	seal thickn. t [mm]	aspect ratio L/t [-]	Bend/ Aero 1/PI [-]	Comment
[5] DLR-F15Lsmod, ref flap, blank seal L20 t0.2												
13.06.25	(57)		30	1	15.2	108.2	blank St.	20	0.2	100	0.07	no data
13.06.25	58		30	1	15.2	108.2	blank St.	20	0.2	100	0.07	
13.06.25	59		35	1	15.2	108.2	blank St.	20	0.2	100	0.10	
13.06.25	60		40	1	15.2	108.2	blank St.	20	0.2	100	0.13	
13.06.25	61		45	1	15.2	108.2	blank St.	20	0.2	100	0.16	
13.06.25	62		50	1	15.2	108.2	blank St.	20	0.2	100	0.20	
13.06.25	63		55	1	15.2	108.2	blank St.	20	0.2	100	0.24	
13.06.25	64		60	1	15.2	108.2	blank St.	20	0.2	100	0.28	
GAP/OVL - TEST												
change seal												
[6] DLR-F15Lsmod, ref flap AR0.45 Gap 15.2, blank seal L80 t0.1												
13.06.25	65		20	1	15.2	108.2	blank St.	80	0.1	800	16	
13.06.25	66		22	1	15.2	108.2	blank St.	80	0.1	800	20	
13.06.25	67		24	1	15.2	108.2	blank St.	80	0.1	800	23	
13.06.25	68		26	1	15.2	108.2	blank St.	80	0.1	800	27	
13.06.25	69		28	1	15.2	108.2	blank St.	80	0.1	800	32	
13.06.25	70		30	1	15.2	108.2	blank St.	80	0.1	800	36	
13.06.25	71		32	1	15.2	108.2	blank St.	80	0.1	800	41	
Mobilkamera installed												
13.06.25	72		32.5	1	15.2	108.2	blank St.	80	0.1	800	43	video 0...34
13.06.25	73		34	1	15.2	108.2	blank St.	80	0.1	800	47	
OvL changed, Gapbracket const.												
Gap-Bracket=17.000, OvL-Bracket=57.000, Gap=14.456, OvL=80.584, Gap-Seal=29.011, Inlet/Outlet=2.01												
[7] DLR-F15Lsmod, minOvL flap AR2.0 Gap 14.5, blank seal L80 t0.1												
13.06.25	74		20	1	14.456	80.584	blank St.	80	0.1	800	16	
13.06.25	75		22	1	14.456	80.584	blank St.	80	0.1	800	20	
13.06.25	76		24	1	14.456	80.584	blank St.	80	0.1	800	23	
13.06.25	77		26	1	14.456	80.584	blank St.	80	0.1	800	27	
13.06.25	78		28	1	14.456	80.584	blank St.	80	0.1	800	32	
13.06.25	79		30	1	14.456	80.584	blank St.	80	0.1	800	36	
13.06.25	80		32	1	14.456	80.584	blank St.	80	0.1	800	41	
13.06.25	81		34	1	14.456	80.584	blank St.	80	0.1	800	47	
13.06.25	82		36	1	14.456	80.584	blank St.	80	0.1	800	52	
13.06.25	83		38	1	14.456	80.584	blank St.	80	0.1	800	58	video U0...38
13.06.25	84		40	1	14.456	80.584	blank St.	80	0.1	800	65	
13.06.25	85		42	1	14.456	80.584	blank St.	80	0.1	800	71	
13.06.25	86		44	1	14.456	80.584	blank St.	80	0.1	800	78	
13.06.25	87		46	1	14.456	80.584	blank St.	80	0.1	800	85	
13.06.25	88		48	1	14.456	80.584	blank St.	80	0.1	800	93	
13.06.25	89		50	1	14.456	80.584	blank St.	80	0.1	800	101	
13.06.25	90		51	1	14.456	80.584	blank St.	80	0.1	800	105	

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Date [MM.DD. JJ]	Data Point [-]	PIV dpt [-]	Speed U [m/sec]	Wing AoA [°]	gap [mm]	overlap OvL [mm]	seal mat. [-]	seal length L [mm]	seal thickn. t [mm]	aspect ratio L/t [-]	Bend/ Aero 1/PI [-]	Comment
13.06.25	91		55	1	14.456	80.584	blank St.	80	0.1	800	122	video U55 &up
16.06.25	92		50	1	14.456	80.538	blank St.	80	0.1	800	101	video U50 down
Gap-OvL changed												
Gap-Bracket=17.591, OvL-Bracket=43.133, Gap=15.200, OvL=95.451, Gap-Seal=15.200, Inlet/Outlet=1.00												
[8] DLR-F15LSmod, flap AR1.0 Gap 15.2, blank seal L80 t0.1												
16.06.25	93		20	1	15.2	95.451	blank St.	80	0.1	800	16	
16.06.25	94		22	1	15.2	95.451	blank St.	80	0.1	800	20	
16.06.25	95		24	1	15.2	95.451	blank St.	80	0.1	800	23	
16.06.25	96		26	1	15.2	95.451	blank St.	80	0.1	800	27	
16.06.25	97		28	1	15.2	95.451	blank St.	80	0.1	800	32	
16.06.25	98		30	1	15.2	95.451	blank St.	80	0.1	800	36	
16.06.25	99		31	1	15.2	95.451	blank St.	80	0.1	800	39	
16.06.25	100		32	1	15.2	95.451	blank St.	80	0.1	800	41	
16.06.25	101		33	1	15.2	95.451	blank St.	80	0.1	800	44	
16.06.25	102		34	1	15.2	95.451	blank St.	80	0.1	800	47	
16.06.25	103		35	1	15.2	95.451	blank St.	80	0.1	800	49	
16.06.25	104		36	1	15.2	95.451	blank St.	80	0.1	800	52	
16.06.25	105		37	1	15.2	95.451	blank St.	80	0.1	800	55	
16.06.25	106		38	1	15.2	95.451	blank St.	80	0.1	800	58	
Gap-OvL changed												
Gap-Bracket=17.372, OvL-Bracket=39.338, Gap=15.200, OvL=98.246, Gap-Seal=11.400, Inlet/Outlet=0.75												
[9] DLR-F15LSmod, flap AR0.75 Gap 15.2, blank seal L80 t0.1												
16.06.25	107		28	1	15.2	98.246	blank St.	80	0.1	800	32	
16.06.25	108		30	1	15.2	98.246	blank St.	80	0.1	800	36	
16.06.25	109		32	1	15.2	98.246	blank St.	80	0.1	800	41	
16.06.25	110		34	1	15.2	98.246	blank St.	80	0.1	800	47	
16.06.25	111		36	1	15.2	98.246	blank St.	80	0.1	800	52	
16.06.25	112		38	1	15.2	98.246	blank St.	80	0.1	800	58	
16.06.25	113		39	1	15.2	98.246	blank St.	80	0.1	800	61	
Gap-OvL changed												
Gap-Bracket=31.736, OvL-Bracket=46.843, Gap=29.200, OvL=90.741, Gap-Seal=22.192, Inlet/Outlet=0.76												
[10] DLR-F15LSmod, flap AR0.75 Gap 29.2, blank seal L80 t0.1												
No Tripping												
16.06.25	114		28	1	29.2	90.741	blank St.	80	0.1	800	32	
16.06.25	115		30	1	29.2	90.741	blank St.	80	0.1	800	36	
16.06.25	116		31	1	29.2	90.741	blank St.	80	0.1	800	39	
16.06.25	117		32	1	29.2	90.741	blank St.	80	0.1	800	41	false comment
16.06.25	118		33.5	1	29.2	90.741	blank St.	80	0.1	800	45	
Flap suction side is tripped: Zigzag tape installed												
16.06.25	119		28	1	29.2	90.741	blank St.	80	0.1	800	32	
16.06.25	120		30	1	29.2	90.741	blank St.	80	0.1	800	36	
16.06.25	121		31	1	29.2	90.741	blank St.	80	0.1	800	39	

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Date [MM.DD. JJ]	Data Point [-]	PIV dpt [-]	Speed U [m/sec]	Wing AoA [°]	gap [mm]	overlap OvL [mm]	seal mat. [-]	seal length L [mm]	seal thickn. t [mm]	aspect ratio L/t [-]	Bend/ Aero 1/PI [-]	Comment
16.06.25	122		32	1	29.2	90.741	blank St.	80	0.1	800	41	false comment
16.06.25	123		33.5	1	29.2	90.741	blank St.	80	0.1	800	45	
Gap-OvL changed												
Gap-Bracket=24.611, OvL-Bracket=43.399, Gap=22.200, OvL=94.185, Gap-Seal=16.650, Inlet/Outlet=0.75												
[12] DLR-F15LSmod, flap AR0.75 Gap 16.65, blank seal L80 t0.1												
16.06.25	124		28	1	22.2	94.185	blank St.	80	0.1	800	32	
16.06.25	125		30	1	22.2	94.185	blank St.	80	0.1	800	36	
16.06.25	126		32	1	22.2	94.185	blank St.	80	0.1	800	41	
16.06.25	127		34	1	22.2	94.185	blank St.	80	0.1	800	47	
16.06.25	128		36	1	22.2	94.185	blank St.	80	0.1	800	52	
16.06.25	129		38	1	22.2	94.185	blank St.	80	0.1	800	58	
16.06.25	130		40	1	22.2	94.185	blank St.	80	0.1	800	65	
16.06.25	131		41	1	22.2	94.185	blank St.	80	0.1	800	68	
16.06.25	132		35	1	22.2	94.185	blank St.	80	0.1	800	49	Viper error
repeat test; different seal properties after operating in non-elastic region?												video
16.06.25	133		30	1	22.2	94.185	blank St.	80	0.1	800	36	
16.06.25	134		32	1	22.2	94.185	blank St.	80	0.1	800	41	
flap removed, PIV-seals installed												
Sensor 5 in flap cove renewed												
indicate whether data contains 5kHz and Harmonics from PIV equipment												
MAIN TEST Phase 1: Wing without flap												
[13] DLR-F15LSmod, no flap, PIV seal L80 t0.5												
23.06.25	(135)		0	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.5	160	0	no data
23.06.25	(136)		0	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.5	160	0	test
23.06.25	(137)		0	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.5	160	0	test
23.06.25	(138)		30	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.5	160	0.3	test
23.06.25	(139)		30	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.5	160	0.3	test
23.06.25	140	X	30	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.5	160	0.3	
23.06.25	141	X	30	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.5	160	0.3	
23.06.25	142		35	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.5	160	0.4	
23.06.25	143		40	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.5	160	0.5	
23.06.25	144		45	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.5	160	0.7	
23.06.25	145		50	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.5	160	0.8	
23.06.25	146		55	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.5	160	1.0	
23.06.25	147	X	60	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.5	160	1.2	
23.06.25	148	X	60	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.5	160	1.2	
23.06.25	149	X	60	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.5	160	1.2	
23.06.25	150	X	60	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.5	160	1.2	
23.06.25	151	X	60	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.5	160	1.2	
23.06.25	152	X	60	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.5	160	1.2	
23.06.25	153	X	60	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.5	160	1.2	
23.06.25	154	X	60	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.5	160	1.2	

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Date [MM.DD. JJ]	Data Point [-]	PIV dpt [-]	Speed U [m/sec]	Wing AoA [°]	gap [mm]	overlap OvL [mm]	seal mat. [-]	seal length L [mm]	seal thickn. t [mm]	aspect ratio L/t [-]	Bend/ Aero 1/PI [-]	Comment
23.06.25	155	X	60	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.5	160	1.2	
23.06.25	156	X	60	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.5	160	1.2	
23.06.25	157		0	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.5	160	0	
change seal												
[14] DLR-F15LSmod, no flap, PIV seal L80 t0.2												
23.06.25	158		0	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.2	400	0	
23.06.25	159		30	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.2	400	4.5	
23.06.25	160		35	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.2	400	6.2	
23.06.25	161		40	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.2	400	8.1	
23.06.25	162		45	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.2	400	10	
23.06.25	163		50	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.2	400	13	
23.06.25	164		55	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.2	400	15	
23.06.25	165	X	60	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.2	400	18	
23.06.25	166	X	60	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.2	400	18	
23.06.25	167		0	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.2	400	0	
change seal												
[15] DLR-F15LSmod, no flap, PIV seal L80 t0.1												
23.06.25	168		50	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.1	800	101	
23.06.25	169		55	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.1	800	122	
23.06.25	170		60	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.1	800	145	
23.06.25	171		30	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.1	800	36	
23.06.25	172		35	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.1	800	49	
23.06.25	173		40	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.1	800	65	
23.06.25	174		45	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.1	800	82	
23.06.25	175	X	60	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.1	800	145	
23.06.25	176	X	60	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.1	800	145	
23.06.25	177	X	60	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.1	800	145	
23.06.25	178	X	60	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.1	800	145	
23.06.25	179	X	60	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.1	800	145	
23.06.25	180	X	60	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.1	800	145	
23.06.25	181	X	60	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.1	800	145	
23.06.25	182	X	60	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.1	800	145	
23.06.25	183	X	60	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.1	800	145	
23.06.25	184	X	60	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.1	800	145	
23.06.25	185		0	1	--	--	PIV Steel	80	0.1	800	0	
remove seal												
[16] DLR-F15LSmod, no flap, no seal												
23.06.25	186		0	1	--	--	holder	--	--	--	--	
23.06.25	187		60	1	--	--	holder	--	--	--	--	
23.06.25	188		35	1	--	--	holder	--	--	--	--	
23.06.25	189		40	1	--	--	holder	--	--	--	--	
23.06.25	190		45	1	--	--	holder	--	--	--	--	

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Date [MM.DD. JJ]	Data Point [-]	PIV dpt [-]	Speed U [m/sec]	Wing AoA [°]	gap [mm]	overlap OvL [mm]	seal mat. [-]	seal length L [mm]	seal thickn. t [mm]	aspect ratio L/t [-]	Bend/ Aero 1/PI [-]	Comment
23.06.25	191		50	1	--	--	holder	--	--	--	--	
23.06.25	192		55	1	--	--	holder	--	--	--	--	
23.06.25	193		60	1	--	--	holder	--	--	--	--	
23.06.25	194	X	60	1	--	--	holder	--	--	--	--	
23.06.25	195	X	60	1	--	--	holder	--	--	--	--	
23.06.25	196	X	60	1	--	--	holder	--	--	--	--	
23.06.25	197	X	60	1	--	--	holder	--	--	--	--	
23.06.25	198	X	60	1	--	--	holder	--	--	--	--	
23.06.25	199	X	60	1	--	--	holder	--	--	--	--	
23.06.25	200	X	60	1	--	--	holder	--	--	--	--	
23.06.25	201	X	60	1	--	--	holder	--	--	--	--	
23.06.25	202	X	60	1	--	--	holder	--	--	--	--	
23.06.25	203	X	60	1	--	--	holder	--	--	--	--	
23.06.25	204		0	1	--	--	holder	--	--	--	--	
remove BL fence												
[17] DLR-F15LSmod, no flap, no seal, no BL fence												
24.06.25	205		0	1	--	--	holder	--	--	--	--	
24.06.25	206		30	1	--	--	holder	--	--	--	--	
24.06.25	207		35	1	--	--	holder	--	--	--	--	
24.06.25	208		40	1	--	--	holder	--	--	--	--	
24.06.25	209		45	1	--	--	holder	--	--	--	--	
24.06.25	210		50	1	--	--	holder	--	--	--	--	
24.06.25	211		55	1	--	--	holder	--	--	--	--	
24.06.25	212		60	1	--	--	holder	--	--	--	--	
24.06.25	213	(-)	60	1	--	--	holder	--	--	--	--	
24.06.25	214	(X)	60	1	--	--	holder	--	--	--	--	
24.06.25	215	(X)	60	1	--	--	holder	--	--	--	--	
Background not dark enough: add black tapes on flap brackets												
24.06.25	216	X	60	1	--	--	holder	--	--	--	--	
24.06.25	217	X	60	1	--	--	holder	--	--	--	--	
24.06.25	218	X	60	1	--	--	holder	--	--	--	--	
24.06.25	219	X	60	1	--	--	holder	--	--	--	--	
24.06.25	220	X	60	1	--	--	holder	--	--	--	--	no psi data
24.06.25	221	X	60	1	--	--	holder	--	--	--	--	
24.06.25	222	X	60	1	--	--	holder	--	--	--	--	
24.06.25	223	X	60	1	--	--	holder	--	--	--	--	
24.06.25	224	X	60	1	--	--	holder	--	--	--	--	
24.06.25	225	X	60	1	--	--	holder	--	--	--	--	
24.06.25	226		0	1	--	--	holder	--	--	--	--	
Installation target: Gap-Bracket=31.736, OvL-Bracket=46.843, Gap=29.200, OvL=90.741, Gap-Seal=22.192, Inlet/Outlet=0.76												
Realised setting: Gap-Bracket=32.086, OvL-Bracket=46.843, Gap=29.550, OvL=90.741, Gap-Seal=22.325, Inlet/Outlet=0.76												
MAIN TEST Phase 2: Wing with flap												

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[18] DLR-F15LSmod, Airbus seal												
check time sync channel for suspicious effects												
25.06.25	227		0	1	29.55	90.741	Airbus	50	3	16.7	--	
25.06.25	228		60	1	29.55	90.741	Airbus	50	3	16.7	--	
25.06.25	229		60	1	29.55	90.741	Airbus	50	3	16.7	--	no time sync
decision: time sync is good, keep time sync channel in measurement												
25.06.25	230		0	1	29.55	90.741	Airbus	50	3	16.7	--	
25.06.25	231		30	1	29.55	90.741	Airbus	50	3	16.7	--	
flap pressure tubes in wind, more tape: taped to model												
25.06.25	232		30	1	29.55	90.741	Airbus	50	3	16.7	--	
25.06.25	233		35	1	29.55	90.741	Airbus	50	3	16.7	--	
25.06.25	234		40	1	29.55	90.741	Airbus	50	3	16.7	--	
25.06.25	235		45	1	29.55	90.741	Airbus	50	3	16.7	--	
25.06.25	236		50	1	29.55	90.741	Airbus	50	3	16.7	--	
25.06.25	237		55	1	29.55	90.741	Airbus	50	3	16.7	--	
25.06.25	238		60	1	29.55	90.741	Airbus	50	3	16.7	--	
25.06.25	239	(X)	60	1	29.55	90.741	Airbus	50	3	16.7	--	
25.06.25	240	X	60	1	29.55	90.741	Airbus	50	3	16.7	--	
25.06.25	241	X	60	1	29.55	90.741	Airbus	50	3	16.7	--	
25.06.25	242	X	60	1	29.55	90.741	Airbus	50	3	16.7	--	
25.06.25	243	X	60	1	29.55	90.741	Airbus	50	3	16.7	--	
25.06.25	244	X	60	1	29.55	90.741	Airbus	50	3	16.7	--	
25.06.25	245	X	60	1	29.55	90.741	Airbus	50	3	16.7	--	
25.06.25	246	X	60	1	29.55	90.741	Airbus	50	3	16.7	--	
25.06.25	247	X	60	1	29.55	90.741	Airbus	50	3	16.7	--	
25.06.25	248	X	60	1	29.55	90.741	Airbus	50	3	16.7	--	
25.06.25	249	X	60	1	29.55	90.741	Airbus	50	3	16.7	--	
25.06.25	250		0	1	29.55	90.741	Airbus	50	3	16.7	--	
change seal; missing/damaged BL fence tape												
[19] DLR-F15LSmod, TPU seal												
25.06.25	251		0	1	29.55	90.741	TPU V2	50	6	8.3	--	
25.06.25	252		30	1	29.55	90.741	TPU V2	50	6	8.3	--	
25.06.25	253		35	1	29.55	90.741	TPU V2	50	6	8.3	--	
25.06.25	254		40	1	29.55	90.741	TPU V2	50	6	8.3	--	
25.06.25	255		45	1	29.55	90.741	TPU V2	50	6	8.3	--	false comment
25.06.25	256		50	1	29.55	90.741	TPU V2	50	6	8.3	--	
25.06.25	257		55	1	29.55	90.741	TPU V2	50	6	8.3	--	false comment
25.06.25	258		60	1	29.55	90.741	TPU V2	50	6	8.3	--	
change seal holder												
[20] DLR-F15LSmod, PIV Steel, L50 t0.1												
26.06.25	259		0	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	50	0.1	500	0	no psi data
26.06.25	260		30	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	50	0.1	500	9	no psi data

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Date [MM.DD. JJ]	Data Point [-]	PIV dpt [-]	Speed U [m/sec]	Wing AoA [°]	gap [mm]	overlap OvL [mm]	seal mat. [-]	seal length L [mm]	seal thickn. t [mm]	aspect ratio L/t [-]	Bend/ Aero 1/PI [-]	Comment
26.06.25	261		35	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	50	0.1	500	12	no psi data
26.06.25	262		40	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	50	0.1	500	16	no psi data
26.06.25	263		45	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	50	0.1	500	20	no psi data
26.06.25	264		50	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	50	0.1	500	25	
26.06.25	265		55	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	50	0.1	500	30	
26.06.25	266		60	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	50	0.1	500	35	
change seal												
[21] DLR-F15LSmod, PIV Steel, L80 t0.1												
26.06.25	267		0	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.12	667	0	
26.06.25	268		28	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.12	667	18	
26.06.25	269		29	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.12	667	20	
26.06.25	270		30	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.12	667	21	
26.06.25	271		31	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.12	667	22	
26.06.25	272		32	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.12	667	24	
26.06.25	273		33	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.12	667	25	
26.06.25	274		34	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.12	667	27	
26.06.25	275		34.3	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.12	667	27	
decision: WT speed 32m/s w/low effect, max WT Speed=34.2 m/s												
target WT speed 32m/s by using control value 33.8m/s												
26.06.25	276	X	32	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.12	667	24	
26.06.25	277	X	32	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.12	667	24	false comment
26.06.25	278	X	32	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.12	667	24	false comment
26.06.25	279	X	32	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.12	667	24	false comment
26.06.25	280	X	32	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.12	667	24	false comment
26.06.25	281	X	32	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.12	667	24	false comment
26.06.25	282	X	32	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.12	667	24	false comment
26.06.25	283	X	32	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.12	667	24	
26.06.25	284	X	32	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.12	667	24	
26.06.25	285	X	32	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.12	667	24	
26.06.25	286	X	32	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.12	667	24	
26.06.25	287		0	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.12	667	0	
target WT speed 34.3m/s by using control value 36.7m/s												
26.06.25	288	(X)	34.3	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.12	667	27	
26.06.25	289	X	34.3	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.12	667	27	
26.06.25	290	X	34.3	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.12	667	27	
26.06.25	291	X	34.3	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.12	667	27	
26.06.25	292	X	34.3	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.12	667	27	
26.06.25	293	X	34.3	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.12	667	27	
26.06.25	294	X	34.3	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.12	667	27	
26.06.25	295	X	34.3	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.12	667	27	
26.06.25	296	X	34.3	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.12	667	27	
26.06.25	297	X	34.3	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.12	667	27	

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Date [MM.DD. JJ]	Data Point [-]	PIV dpt [-]	Speed U [m/sec]	Wing AoA [°]	gap [mm]	overlap OvL [mm]	seal mat. [-]	seal length L [mm]	seal thickn. t [mm]	aspect ratio L/t [-]	Bend/ Aero 1/PI [-]	Comment
26.06.25	298	X	34.3	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.12	667	27	
26.06.25	299		0	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.12	667	0	
change seal												
[22] DLR-F15LSmod, PIV Steel, L80 t0.2												
26.06.25	300		0	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.22	364	0	
26.06.25	301		30	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.22	364	3.4	
26.06.25	302		35	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.22	364	4.6	
26.06.25	303		40	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.22	364	6.1	
26.06.25	304		45	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.22	364	7.7	
26.06.25	305		50	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.22	364	9.5	
26.06.25	306		55	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.22	364	11	
26.06.25	307		60	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.22	364	14	
26.06.25	308		63.5	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.22	364	15	
26.06.25	309	(X)	60	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.22	364	14	T=32°C high
26.06.25	310	X	60	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.22	364	14	
26.06.25	311	X	60	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.22	364	14	
26.06.25	312	X	60	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.22	364	14	
26.06.25	313	X	60	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.22	364	14	
26.06.25	314	X	60	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.22	364	14	
26.06.25	315	X	60	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.22	364	14	
26.06.25	316	X	60	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.22	364	14	
26.06.25	317	X	60	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.22	364	14	
26.06.25	318	X	60	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.22	364	14	
26.06.25	319	X	60	1	29.55	90.741	PIV Steel	80	0.22	364	14	
remove seal												
[23] DLR-F15LSmod, no seal												
26.06.25	320	X	34.3	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
26.06.25	321	X	34.3	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
26.06.25	322	X	34.3	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
26.06.25	323	X	34.3	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
26.06.25	324	X	34.3	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
26.06.25	325	X	34.3	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
26.06.25	326	X	34.3	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
26.06.25	327	X	34.3	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
26.06.25	328	X	34.3	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
26.06.25	329	X	34.3	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
26.06.25	330	X	60	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
26.06.25	331	X	60	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
26.06.25	332	X	60	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
26.06.25	333	X	60	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
26.06.25	334	X	60	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
26.06.25	335	X	60	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	

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Date [MM.DD. JJ]	Data Point [-]	PIV dpt [-]	Speed U [m/sec]	Wing AoA [°]	gap [mm]	overlap OvL [mm]	seal mat. [-]	seal length L [mm]	seal thickn. t [mm]	aspect ratio L/t [-]	Bend/ Aero 1/PI [-]	Comment
26.06.25	336	X	60	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
26.06.25	337	X	60	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
26.06.25	338	X	60	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
26.06.25	339	X	60	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
27.06.25	340		0	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
27.06.25	341		28	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	false comment
27.06.25	342		29	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
27.06.25	343		30	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
27.06.25	344		31	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
27.06.25	345		32	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
27.06.25	346		33	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
27.06.25	347		34	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
27.06.25	348		34.3	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
27.06.25	349		35	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
27.06.25	350		40	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
27.06.25	351		45	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
27.06.25	352		50	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
27.06.25	353		55	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
27.06.25	354		60	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
27.06.25	355		63.5	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
de-rigging of PIV test setup by DLR-GO, repeat last build with clean background												
[24] DLR-F15LSmod, no seal												
27.06.25	356		0	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
27.06.25	357		30	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
27.06.25	358		32	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
27.06.25	359		34.3	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
27.06.25	360		35	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
27.06.25	361		40	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
27.06.25	362		45	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
27.06.25	363		50	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
27.06.25	364		55	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
27.06.25	365		60	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
27.06.25	366		63.5	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
HOTWIRE TEST - accompanying VIPER data points												
Hotwire rigging												
ISEL Traverse adjusted for flap cove												
[25] DLR-F15LSmod, no seal, hotwire, flap cove: COVE34												
07.07.25	367		34.3	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
07.07.25	368		34.3	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
07.07.25	369		34.3	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
07.07.25	370		34.3	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
07.07.25	371		34.3	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	

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Date [MM.DD. JJ]	Data Point [-]	PIV dpt [-]	Speed U [m/sec]	Wing AoA [°]	gap [mm]	overlap OvL [mm]	seal mat. [-]	seal length L [mm]	seal thickn. t [mm]	aspect ratio L/t [-]	Bend/ Aero 1/PI [-]	Comment
[25] DLR-F15LSmod, no seal, hotwire, flap cove: COVE60												
07.07.25	372		60	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
07.07.25	373		60	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
07.07.25	374		60	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
07.07.25	375		60	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	no psi
[25] DLR-F15LSmod, no seal, hotwire, wake downstream flap trailing edge: FLPT60												
[25] DLR-F15LSmod, no seal, hotwire, wake downstream flap trailing edge: FLPT34												
07.07.25	(376)		60	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	no psi
[25] DLR-F15LSmod, no seal, hotwire, flap cove: COVE2_34												
08.07.25	(377)		34.3	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	bad dpt
08.07.25	378		34.3	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
08.07.25	379		34.3	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	
08.07.25	380		34.3	1	29.55	90.741	holder	--	--	--	--	

6. Test deliverables

The following data can be delivered by DLR:

- Test photos
- Test rig data
 - mean values, table by datapoint
- Surface pressure sensor and out-of-flow microphone:
 - 1 Hz Frequency-resolved data (PSD) (mainly for the identification of tones for $f < 1000\text{Hz}$)
 - 10Hz Frequency-resolved data (SPL)
 - time-resolved data (only if the need is specified)
- Seal surveillance camera videos
- Hotwire test data
- CAD-Data for the numerical cases and test benchmark